

Harmonic Audio Object Processing in Frequency Domain

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Abstract

The aim of this thesis work is the transformation of timing, time duration and fundamental frequency of audio objects like single notes or a melody line of one instrument within a polyphonic audio environment. The research is limited to harmonic audio objects which are comprised of a series of frequency partials sharing a quasi-harmonic interval relation among them. With this percussive sounds of stochastic nature without sinusoidal content are excluded while the stochastic component as intrinsic part of different instruments is considered because of its perceptual significance.

A priori knowledge about the pitch and timing of each note is required from a MIDI file including several mono tracks. Thus no probabilistic estimation of the concurrent number of sources and the pitch and timing of note events is considered and to be expected errors are omitted.

In contrary to well-known fields of research like source separation or audio decomposition into single mono tracks, the research work as well as the application implemented for this thesis estimates the harmonic partials, the transient part of each note onset and the stochastic residual belonging to one audio object without iteratively subtracting the estimation results from the input stream.

Before synthesis musically meaningful transformations like time-scaling or pitch-shifting along with their corresponding scaling factor, the shifting of audio objects in time or the substitution of audio objects by other instrument types are considered.

The re-synthesized audio output will be examined by subjective listening and objective evaluation tests against a reference output where the same transformation got applied to the corresponding audio object of the monophonic track before mixing all tracks together.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

All we do is reverse-engineering this world; if god would give us the source code, we would be jobless - Indian phrase

1.1 Motivation

With the evolution of the availability and massive online distribution of music over the last decade, desires of listening consumers arise to remix their favourite songs, to creatively modify the content of the consumed music and to produce new musical variations of them, a mash up. Some artists started to provide on the internet the complete data set of their studio production system like single audio samples and loops, MIDI data and the project files of the software sequencer chosen in order to enable consumers to remix their songs easily. Mostly unknown music producers supply their creative output freely under the Creative Commons¹ license. As with not freely available music from commercial labels, most music is submitted as one polyphonic stream in mono, joint-stereo or stereo which destroys the possibility to transform single audio objects.

The human auditory system is able to perform accurate stream segregation and provides a sophisticated auditory scene analysis. Several complementary research areas comprised in the annual MIREX competition ² like Audio Onset detection, Audio Chord detection, Audio Melody Extraction and Multiple Fundamental Frequency Estimation and Tracking aim to automatically transcribe music content, but fail in achieving an highly accurate transcription. Different technological paradigms are applied to model the human auditory system and its processes for perception and

¹www.creativecommons.org

²www.music-ir.org/mirex/

cognition. Probabilistic hypotheses and different signal processing methods heuristically aim to accomplish a sophisticated estimation and transcription of the audio content. Still the current state of the art could not succeed in providing reasonable results and the problem is considered as one of the holy grails in the area of music processing.

(Blind) Source separation and decomposition algorithms like sparse approximation fit signal models to the underlying audio data but cannot distinct between single instruments types and melody lines.

1.2 Inspiration

Latest in March 2008 at the Musikmesse ³ in Frankfurt, Germany, the commercial software Melodyne from the company Celemony ⁴ gained much attention with their Direct Note Access (DNA) called technology which automatically detects chords of especially piano- and guitar-like sounds and enables their modification in musically meaningful ways. Failures in the detection for especially complex polyphonic content can be corrected by the user. Instruments sharing the same fundamental frequency f_0 at the same time are treated as one audio object. The automatic recognition of instrument types and classes and the assignment of single notes to a grouped melody line trajectory is indicated to be solved in the future. Melodyne stores the estimated note tracks into a MIDI file as output but does not accept a MIDI file as input to steer the estimation process.

Figure 1.1: DNA example from a mixed polyphonic channel to separated monophonic channels

A semi-automatic approach requiring manual corrections by the user in order to

³<http://musik.messefrankfurt.com>

⁴www.celemony.com

split audio content into its components is provided by the german software company ProSoniq with the software sonicWORX ⁵. As well no MIDI input is required and the decomposition task is relied on a powerful pattern tracking algorithm plus user interaction on a high-qualitative time-frequency representation.

Figure 1.2: Example of the sonicWORX semi-manual approach

1.3 Scope

To facilitate the remixing of music pieces the objective for this research work is to investigate the supervised transformation of single audio objects in a polyphonic environment utilizing a MIDI file as additional timing and f_0 input. Since MIDI files are commonly available for mostly commercial hit songs, a final user application can align the MIDI description to the audio content, does not have to estimate all music sequencer tracks and their audio events with expected errors and provides with this an accurate remixing tool. The user could additionally apply manual corrections in a final application being out of the scope for this research work.

The main research objective of this work is to solve the critical part of the detection, estimation and tracking of the frequency partials belonging to harmonic audio objects. The work effort is concentrated on the treatment of overlapping partials of different audio sources, a sophisticated estimation and prediction of harmonic partials and their trajectories for high-fidelity audio quality along with consideration of amplitude and frequency modulations.

⁵www.prosoniq.com/editing-products/sonicworx/

Chapter 2

Methodology

Research is what I'm doing when I don't know what I'm doing - Werner von Braun

2.1 Software Environment

The chosen software environment to implement, test and develop all algorithms for this research work is Matlab. The software system consists of the blocks depicted in figure 2.1.

Different M synthesized monophonic tracks are mixed together into one polyphonic single-channel stream, segmented into overlapping frames, windowed by an analysis window and transformed to the frequency domain with an FFT. An additional track for background noise may be added for different test setups to account for the influence of stochastic sounds from percussive instruments. The additional f0 and timing information are aligned to each frame for the further processing in the frequency domain. The block diagram does not exemplify the processing of one song in an offline-like manner. The STFT in the analysis part is first successively executed frame-wise for the whole music piece in order to receive a compact time-frequency plane (TF). The same paradigm is executed in a second evaluation employing a time-frequency representation as discussed in chapter 3.3.8.

The harmonic estimation block identifies the magnitudes and frequencies of the harmonic partials describing the deterministic part of the consecutive harmonic audio objects of one monophonic track. The global residual can be estimated by employing the Spectral Modelling Synthesis (SMS) technique, as defined in [Serra, 1989], by subtracting the sinusoidal content for each monophonic track from the compact TF. The global residual ideally includes no deterministic but all stochastic parts of harmonic instruments plus the background noise. The global residual can be transformed

Figure 2.1: SW system block diagram

to a new TF along with each estimated deterministic part of the monophonic tracks. For the latter ones a transformation process to time-scale, time-shift or pitch-shift may be applied, described by the output score.

2.2 Test Setup

A known score, described by a multitrack MIDI file, is utilized to synthesize each MIDI monotrack into one monophonic audio file. The same transformation algorithm applied later in the polyphonic environment to one, several or all audio objects of one monotrack is applied to its corresponding representation in the frequency domain of the monophonic stream. A reference output Ref is created by mixing M different monophonic audio streams together, with a transformation and processing function eventually applied to them in advance, as depicted in figure 2.2.

The corresponding reference input is created by mixing the same monophonic audio streams together without any transformation applied in advance, as depicted in figure 2.3. The task for the software system is now to produce ideally the same system output waveform Sys as the reference output. The system output Sys is created in the polyphonic environment by estimating the harmonic partials belonging to each monophonic stream, applying the same processing functions like pitch-shifting or time-stretching to the same audio objects and re-synthesizing the to a new time-frequency plane transformed content to the system output waveform Sys .

Figure 2.2: SW system for reference output creation

Figure 2.3: SW system for system output creation

The execution of the same transformation algorithms beforehand instead of letting a synthesizer, steered by a multitrack MIDI file containing the same transformations applied, generate the reference output avoids that the synthesizer might use different samples producing the reference output. With this approach the same transformations applied to the monophonic and polyphonic signals are compared. A final objective and subjective evaluation will express how the quality of the transformation(s) applied degrades with polyphonic signals. The MIDI score as event-based description of the audio objects and tracks is employed as an additional input to supervise the detection of notes in the time-frequency representation. The score is modified according to the applied processing function to identify the audio objects in the new transformed time-frequency plane.

For each new test setup with different polyphonic content and/or different transformations applied, the following steps are executed.

1. Analyze the mono signal and compute its time-frequency plane.
2. Transform the audio by generating a new time-frequency plane where both scores can be used to identify and modify the audio objects.

3. Obtain the output sound from the transformed time-frequency plane.
4. Compute an error function comparing the transformed output signals to the original transformation (objective evaluation).
5. Conduct a listening test (subjective evaluation).

2.3 Objective Evaluation

The objective measurement is given by calculating the difference of the systems output and the pre-stored reference output. The difference between both audio streams is expressed by an Euclidean Distance (ED) measure employing the perceptual meaningful audio descriptors MFCC, LPC and LSF. For each re-synthesized wavefile pair of reference output *Ref* created in a monophonic and system output *Sys* created in a polyphonic environment, both audio streams are transformed to the spectral domain to compute the perceptual feature vectors MFCC, LPC and LSF.

The perceptual feature vectors actually would provide a good measurement of the perceived change because of describing the spectral envelope and with this the timbral sound character of audio data. But since the aim of the applied note processing transformation intends to preserve the spectral envelope, especially for pitch-shifting in the spectral domain, these measurements might neglect perceptual changes. Therefore the measurement of the magnitude spectrum in different frequency bands could create feature vectors for the objective evaluation as well.

The cumulative distance is calculated between the corresponding elements of the feature vectors and defined by equation 2.1, with M being the number of coefficients per frame for one feature vector and N indices all frames for one test setup.

$$ED_{feature}(Ref, Sys) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M (Ref_n(m) - Sys_n(m))^2} \quad (2.1)$$

A second objective measurement on the feature vectors is the Pearson Correlation, as introduced in [Pearson, 1900] and defined by equation 2.2 with the sample means \bar{X} and \bar{Y} and the sample standard deviations s_X and s_Y for reference output X and system output Y. This product-moment correlation weights how proportional the values of two variables are to each other. A linear relation between two vectors produces a high correlation expressing their linear dependence and reflects the degree of relation between both vectors.

$$r = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{X_i - \bar{X}}{s_X} \right) \left(\frac{Y_i - \bar{Y}}{s_Y} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

The Pearson coefficient r is defined within the range of $[-1, 1]$ with $r=1$ expressing a perfect linear relationship between both variables, while $r=0$ refers to no correlation and -1 gives a perfect negative correlation.

2.4 Subjective Evaluation

The subjective measurement is accomplished through listening tests and should validate any result of the objective evaluation measurement. After each test execution while the incremental development of the software a rough listening test pre-evaluates a possible improvement in quality of a new or modified algorithmic part in addition to the objective measure.

After the finalization of the programming part for this research work a listening test is conducted online to examine the perceived qualitative performance of the implemented methods with different algorithmic setups and signal processing paradigms on the same audio test environment and as well on different audio test setups in terms of instruments and polyphony.

For this a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) test as a generalization of a Student's t-test for more than two distributions is planned to be set up in conjunction with a Tukey test. MANOVA as explained in [Hair, 2006] or [Bray and Maxwell, 1985] finds significant differences between mean values for groups of variables by comparing their variances. A variance is the sum of squared deviations from the overall mean, divided by its degree of freedom, as defined in equation 2.3.

$$s^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (x - \hat{x})^2 \quad (2.3)$$

This is well suited to evaluate the quality of different system outputs for different algorithmic setups for the same test input against one reference. As well the grouping of the same variables like the same amount of polyphony or the same instrument type applied for analysis is possible. The overall variance is partitioned into the error within-group variability and components exhibiting the differences between their mean values to be evaluated, which are for this work the groups different algorithmic setups, different instruments selected and different polyphonies tested.

The reference output is being compared for each test setup defined in the first column, like different instruments or polyphony against different algorithmic setups. The repeated measure factor expresses repeated measurements of the same variable system output Sys on the same subject or group combination polyphony and instrument type(s) and is placed horizontally in table 2.1. The between groups factor expresses the variances between the vertically placed groups polyphony and instrument type(s) and groups one algorithmic setup together over different polyphony and

instrument combinations. The dependent variables are the results of each single test described by the mean distribution while the independent variables are the different groups manipulated in the test setup in order to cover different aspects for the evaluation of the data.

Table 2.1: Subjective evaluation - Example test setup

Polyphony = P Instrument type = It	Algorithm 1	Algorithm 2	Algorithm 3
P=2; It 1+2	μ_{11}	μ_{12}	μ_{13}
P=3; It 1+2	μ_{21}	μ_{22}	μ_{23}
P=2; It 2+3	μ_{31}	μ_{32}	μ_{33}
P=3; It 2+3	μ_{41}	μ_{42}	μ_{43}

MANOVA computes the within-group variability being the error variance Mean Square Error MS_{err} , the total variability of the overall mean and the between groups variability Mean Square Effect MS_{eff} . Since MANOVA only provides a significant difference between groups of mean values but does not exhibit the encountered difference between which groups of mean distribution, the Tukey test additionally performs *a posteriori* pairwise comparisons of mean values in order to determine a possibly statistically significant difference above a threshold between certain means if the Null hypothesis H_0 got rejected.

The Tukey test begins with the highest mean value and evaluates it against all other mean values in ascending order from the lowest mean value. For each comparison the Null hypothesis $H_0 : \mu_{xx} = \mu_{yy}$ stating that no significant difference between the compared mean values μ_{xx} and μ_{yy} occurs is evaluated. H_0 is rejected and the alternative hypothesis H_1 is validated if a significant difference above the critical value α of usually 5% probability is found.

Comparing more than two groups at once by evaluating the global Null hypothesis H_0 by the analysis of variance via pair-wise t-tests accumulates the alpha error and is therefore not applicable.

The persons are asked to judge how much difference they could hear between one reference and each system output for one test setup. A scale of 0 for worst and 5 for best quality of the system output is given. The overall mean and variance for each test distribution is calculated to retrieve statistical significances and validate or reject the objective measurements.

Chapter 3

State of the Art

The most joy in life comes from my violin - Albert Einstein

This chapter explains technologies from different fields of investigation being relevant for this research work and building the State of the Art basis to start with.

3.1 Signal Separation

The separation from single-channel signals state a maximally underdetermined problem.

Mark Every provides a series of research work being the main starting point for the signal or source estimation of harmonic partials for this research approach. In [Every and Szymanski, 2004] the same supervised approach employing f0 and timing information is introduced and [Every, 2006] provides an elaborative explanation about the investigations executed and technologies employed. Several interweaving sound sources from mono recordings are mixed into a polyphonic single-channel stream and signal separation algorithms are executed. A frame-wise spectral filter is constructed for each harmonic while two filter shapes separate overlapping harmonics. First the mix is transcribed into separate instrument sources by removing note-wise the harmonic partials assigned to each instrument and secondly the separation process is performed which loses some information about the audio objects.

The investigation found that the MIDI information about f0 and the vibrato rate/depth is insufficient for a high fidelity quality. Thus monophonic f0 techniques are employed to provide a frame-based score information. This requires an effective method to detect prominent spectral peaks providing an accurate time-varying pitch continuation information and to design filter notches depending on the predicted frequencies and amplitudes of sinusoidal peaks. The spectral filter for one harmonic

partial has a unit amplitude across the main lobe until neighbouring valleys but does not remove sidelobes. The residual is obtained by subtracting a sum of sinusoids from the input spectrum which contains energy from the sidelobes of harmonic sinusoids due to the not accurate sinusoidal subtraction.

3.2 Sparse Approximation and Atomic Decomposition

Goodwin discusses in [Goodwin, 1997] the usage of basis expansions and their shortcomings to be overcome by over-complete expansions like best bases, adaptive Wavelet packets, over-sampled filter banks and generalized time-frequency decompositions. The Matching Pursuit (MP) algorithm is a parametric atomic decomposition adapting to a signal from an overcomplete dictionary of time-frequency atoms. Different dictionaries like Gabor, MDCT, Wavelets or heuristically learned can be employed to correlate signal excerpts with the dictionary atoms. The atoms achieving the highest correlation are selected iteratively until no signal components is left for explanation. With this the signal is decomposed into elementary waveforms which provide better transformation properties than complex interrelated signal components. Goodwin considers dictionaries of damped sinusoids and asymmetric atoms for perfect reconstruction.

Further development based on this MP approach was executed by Sturm, which is best summarized in [Bobby Lee Townsend Sturm, 2009]. Easy transformation possibilities are shown in [Sturm et al., 2006] raising interest for this research work but is only listed as interesting technology fulfilling similar purposes. Sturm interprets these dictionary-based methods (DBMs) as basis for granular synthesis algorithms, as is the Fourier transform for additive synthesis.

In [Derrien, 2007] a multi-scale Gabor analysis, being a modified version of the Matching pursuit algorithm, provides a redundant time-frequency dictionary of Gabor waveforms for decomposition and time-scaling of single audio object.

3.3 Signal Estimation

3.3.1 Sinusoidal Modelling

The Fourier transform describes any signal as a finite sum of sinus and cosinus functions while sinusoidal modelling describes the time-varying amplitudes, frequencies and phases of deterministic components. This approach presupposes sinusoidal components and is due to fail for exclusive noise parts without clear sinusoidal peaks. Sinusoidal without residual modelling clearly introduces not a perfect reconstruction

and accepts the loss of perceptual information for the purpose of better parametric transformation properties.

The sinusoidal model in equation 3.1 describes the deterministic part of the signal $x(t)$ with time-varying amplitudes a_n , the initial phases ϕ and the time-varying phases θ being determined by frequency f_n and described by $\omega_n = 2\pi f_n t$.

$$x(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n(t) \cdot \cos(\theta(t) + \phi) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n(t) \cdot \cos(\omega_n(t) + \phi) \quad (3.1)$$

Levine applies sinusoidal modelling in [Levine et al., 1998] to perform high-quality time-stretching and pitch-shifting on polyphonic audio. A multiresolution approach estimates the parameters by splitting the signal into octave-spaced, non-aliased subbands to perform sinusoidal modeling on each subband signal individually.

A sinusoidal model is a parametric method, does not guarantee perfect reconstruction because of neglecting the transient and residual part and adapts from the signal the model parameters to time-frequency atoms in the analysis process.

3.3.2 Spectral Modelling Synthesis

The modelling of inharmonic components is required because of its perceptual attribute of sound. A time-varying noise envelope has to be introduced to the output time-frequency plane for each estimated mono source. The deterministic plus stochastic model considers additionally to the sinusoidal modelling the residual part being comprised of stochastic noise-like components, as introduced and discussed in [Serra, 1989], [Serra and Smith, 1990] and [Serra, 1997]. The residual is obtained by the subtraction of all detected sinusoidal components and the modelling of the remaining noise envelope through interpolation. The deterministic plus stochastic model achieves as well no perfect reconstruction but does not neglect the perceptually important stochastic part.

The problem for the processing of single harmonic audio objects in a polyphonic environment is the superimposition of different sources and their deterministic plus stochastic components. The modelling of (overlapped) sinusoidal peaks is discussed in the following chapters. The estimation of the global envelope is addressed in chapter 3.3.4 while approaches to treat the "local" noise envelope for each harmonic source is discussed in this chapter.

The envelope for the residual is modelled by weighting functions approximating the white noise contour while retaining phase information for re-synthesis, as mentioned in [M.R. and J.E., 2005].

3.3.3 Transient Modelling

The processing of transients in the context of time-scaling and pitch-shifting with phase vocoder techniques leads to transients smearing into following frames. Transient parts can therefore be copied directly to the output time-frequency plane while setting the time-scaling or pitch-shifting factor to the duration of the transient to one and reinitializing the phase propagation in the phase vocoder. The transient onset time instant for this supervised approach is roughly known from the MIDI input while the transient offset time needs to be estimated. An initial heuristically set time threshold for each transient of all instrument types and with this an amount of spectral frames being the transient lengths may be applicable for a monophonic audio stream but cannot assure to exclude exactly sinusoidal contents from the attack or sustained note part. Transient detection and modelling improves therefore the overall quality of the proposed system for this work and is especially necessary for polyphonic audio streams where pure sinusoidal components from one monophonic stream overlap with attack transients of a starting note from another monophonic stream.

In [Nsabimana and Zoelzer, 2008] an unsupervised transient detection and modelling is executed in the context of audio signal decomposition for a later time- and pitch-scaling. The handling of transients is discussed in an Overlap-and-Add context which requires the copying of the transient part to several overlapping frames.

Different techniques or signal descriptors to detect transients are the energy signals first derivative, measurements of the spectral dissimilarity, high frequency content (HFC) or Mel-cepstrum coefficients, as summarized in [Karrer et al., 2006].

The approach taken for this research is based on the works in [Roebel, 2003a], [Roebel, 2003b] and [Roebel, 2005] which address not just the detection of transients in general on a time basis but distinguish peak-wise between their correspondence to a true sinusoidal component, or as being part of an attack transient. This is essential for a phase vocoder implementation in a polyphonic environment in order to reduce possible artefacts by avoiding to apply the phase vocoder processing techniques to peaks of the attack transient and to reset the propagated phase for each transient peak, while as well retaining the vertical phase relation between peaks of an attack transient event. Continuing the phase vocoders phase propagation as explained in chapter 3.5.2 over an attack transient leads to an artefact effect called transient smearing because the transient event has no relation to the preceding phase evolution of the signal.

Phase reinitialization for transient peaks retains the transients shape. Sinusoidal peaks from other sources remain untouched and the factor of time-scaling does not have to be set to one if the center of the analysis window is close to the transient event. An attack is modelled in [Roebel, 2003a] by a linear ramp with saturation. The analysis window is moved over an attack to execute a following STFT. The region around each sinusoidal peak until the first appearing valley on both sides is integrated

in order to calculate its center of gravity (COG) of the instantaneous energy of the windowed signal, defined by equation 3.2 for continuous signals.

$$t_{cg} = \frac{\int_{\omega_l}^{\omega_h} -\frac{\partial\phi(\omega, t_m)}{\partial\omega} A(\omega, t_m)^2 d\omega}{\int_{\omega_l}^{\omega_h} A(\omega, t_m)^2 d\omega} \quad (3.2)$$

The term $-\frac{\partial\phi(\omega, t_m)}{\partial\omega}$ denotes the negative phase derivative being the group delay which expresses the contribution of the frequencies ω_l to ω_h (in radians) to the peak. Equation 3.3 denotes the integration as a sum over the DFT bins for a quasi-stationary assumption.

$$t_{cg} = \frac{\sum_{\omega_l}^{\omega_h} -\phi(\omega, t_m) A(\omega, t_m)^2}{\sum_{\omega_l}^{\omega_h} A(\omega, t_m)^2} \quad (3.3)$$

Moving the analysis window in time from left to right over an attack transient locates the COG to different positions which is described by the following enumeration explaining the general transient detection in steps.

1. The COG is placed initially to the right of the window center, leading to a negative phase derivative on average.
2. Moving further locates the COG towards the left side and decreases the phase slope.
3. A phase region with zero slope and a peak with minimum bandwidth indicates a window position being located completely over the attack transient.

3.3.4 Frequency Adaptive Noise Level Estimation

The standard phase vocoder will introduce errors when sub-harmonic and spurious peaks are treated as sinusoidal components. Hence a peak detection above a frequency-dependent threshold is required to minimize the influence of spurious spectral peaks and noise components. This is especially mandatory for a polyphonic audio stream where different sources heterodyne their sinusoidal and residual components.

The detection of prominent peaks using a frequency-dependent threshold for signal separation is addressed in [Every and Szymanski, 2004], [Every and Szymanski, 2006] and [Every, 2006]. In the first place a convolution $Env(f)^c$ of the complex FFT spectrum with the input window of type Hanning with a length $1 + N_{win}/64$ is computed, with the parameter c set to a range of $[0.5, 1]$ in [Every and Szymanski, 2004] or [Every, 2006] to flatten the envelope with smaller values. The resulting envelope is divided from the amplitude spectrum. The convolution emphasizes sinusoidal

components which share a similar shape with the convoluted spectral representation of a Hanning window and suppresses stochastic influences. A division of the amplitude spectrum by the result of the convolution subtracts all sinusoidal content and reveals the noise level contour of the spectrum. The division is explained in [Every and Szymanski, 2004] but left out in [Every and Szymanski, 2006] and [Every, 2006].

This approach suffers from spectral peaks with amplitudes above the estimated noise level resulting from peaks not resembling the spectral shape of the windowing function and could therefore not correlate well in the convolution process and not be subtracted accurate enough with the division. Therefore an adaptive resonance bandwidth is employed in [Every, 2006] to span the main spectral lobe to different widths. This addresses as well non-stationary modulations which broaden the spectral peak bandwidth.

Yeh applies in [Yeh, 2008] for a multiple f_0 estimation approach which won the MIREX competition 2008¹ as well a frequency-adaptive noise level estimation to distinguish between sinusoidal and spurious peaks. A noise model represents the noise envelope as a frequency-dependent spectral envelope. Assumptions about the sinusoidal and residual components supervise the spectral envelope estimation of noise components which classifies spectral peaks as sinusoids or noise.

The assumptions are:

- Flat noise spectrum with a nearly constant magnitude within a narrow band
- Filtered white noise with a frequency-dependent smoothing function
- Noise is modelled as a succession of Rayleigh distributions
- If the amplitude distribution is Gaussian white noise, then the spectral magnitude is a Rayleigh distribution

Figure 3.1 depicts to the left a Gaussian distribution describing white noise and to the right the magnitude distribution of Gaussian white noise, modelled as a Rayleigh distribution.

Because of this assumptions Yeh fits the magnitude distribution of noise components in each narrow band to a Rayleigh distribution which describes with different modes the spectral distribution of filtered white noise. A Probability Density Function (PDF) of spectral peak magnitudes x and the mode σ of the Rayleigh distribution as standard deviation is given by equation 3.4.

¹http://www.music-ir.org/mirex/2008/index.php/Multiple_Fundamental_Frequency_Estimation.%26-Tracking-Results

Figure 3.1: Gaussian and Rayleigh distribution, adopted from [Yeh, 2008]

$$p(x) = \frac{x}{\sigma^2} \cdot e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}}; 0 \leq x < \infty, \sigma > 0 \quad (3.4)$$

This noise model describes a probabilistic noise level and determines the Rayleigh distribution mode σ best fitting to the distribution in each narrow band. The probability of an observed peak to be a spurious noise component is high for magnitude peaks $< \sigma$ and low for magnitudes $> \sigma$. Different modes σ of a Rayleigh distribution are shown with figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Different Rayleigh distribution modes σ , adopted from [Yeh, 2008]

The final frequency-dependent noise level is approached similarly to the cepstrum-based true-envelope (TE) estimation introduced in [Villavicencio et al., 2006] and [Villavicencio et al., 2007] which iteratively updates the estimation order until the best fitting spectral envelope estimation is reached. Here an iterative evaluation and adaptation of the noise level is executed until all Rayleigh distributions are fitted for all narrow bands. With this the spectral peaks are iteratively classified into sinusoidal components above and noise components below the current noise level until all identified noise peaks coherently explain the estimated noise level. A probabilistic threshold is set relative to the noise level.

3.3.5 Peak Detection and Interpolation

The detection of magnitude peaks in the spectrum is straightforward when relying on a good estimation of the noise level. A local maxima is found if the two neighbouring frequency bins possess a lower amplitude and all addressed bins exhibit a magnitude above the noise level threshold. Fitting a parabola to the three bins implements parabolic interpolation, as mentioned in [Bonada, 2000] and expressed by equation 3.5 with a being a measure of concavity, p the center of the parabola and b the offset on the vertical axis.

$$y(x) = a(x - p)^2 + b \quad (3.5)$$

The interpolation of spectral peaks to their true centre frequency to describe the frequency of one sinusoidal component is achieved using the barycentric interpolation for Hamming windows in [Every and Szymanski, 2004], which refers to the work in [Donadio, 1999] about the interpolation of frequency peaks. The barycentric interpolation is told to achieve better quality for source separation compared to parabolic or other interpolation techniques. The peak interpolation needs to be distinct between peaks belonging to one or several harmonic partials for this research work.

Figure 3.3: Example: Interpolation to the true frequency 236.9 Hz from 6 DFT bins

The unavoidable interpolation of the frequency-shifted spectral content to discrete frequency bins introduces sinusoidal modulation in the time domain. The analysis windowing function $h(n)$ becomes modulated by the sinus function, expressed in equation 3.6.

$$h_m(n) = h(n) \cdot \sin\left(\pi \frac{n}{N}\right) \quad (3.6)$$

Other interpolation schemata than linear interpolation like Lagrange interpolation or all-pass approximation minimizes this effect, as mentioned in [Laroche, 1999]. Also employing a FFT of size N being much larger than the window size T avoids this problem.

3.3.6 Instantaneous f0 estimation

The initial approach proposed for this work relied exclusively on timing and fundamental frequency for each note from a MIDI file. This does not rely on frame-wise f0 information describing the rate and depth of a possible vibrato occurring. Instead we employ a pre-annotated score from a pre-analysis for each monophonic track, using the f0 estimation algorithms explained in this chapter.

A loose frame-wise peak estimation plus a phase vocoder approach is likely to select a different peak trajectory as the same peak continuation. Therefore the freely available YIN algorithm as proposed in [de Cheveigne and Kawahara, 2002] and the two-way mismatch procedure in [Maher and Beauchamp, 1993] from Maher and Beauchamp is an additional part of the software system for this research approach.

A monophonic f0 estimation algorithm is by nature not suited to estimate several overlapping instantaneous frequencies. It would randomly stick to one of the occurring f0 sources. But both monophonic f0 estimation algorithms explained in the following sub-chapters can be utilized or modified to estimate the exact instantaneous frequency of one source when applying *a priori* knowledge from the MIDI input. The most likely instantaneous frequency per frame is employed to improve the transformation process.

The two-way mismatch algorithm can be modified to exclusively evaluate the occurrence of the fundamental frequencies known from the multitrack MIDI file. Per f0 candidate from the MIDI file a series of candidates being close to this frequency within an assumed frequency range not exceeding the expected range of possible vibrato frequency depth is given to the two-way mismatch algorithm. The same approach is executed with the YIN algorithm which evaluates the correlation result and searches for a prominent peak within a given frequency range around the *a priori* known true f0 frequency without any frequency modulation.

3.3.6.1 YIN

The YIN algorithm employs and finally combines the results of different f0 estimation techniques by using the AMDF and Autocorrelation (ACR) method as basic estimation algorithm and applying improvements in the post-processing step to minimize f0 estimation errors.

Autocorrelation:

The autocorrelation procedure along with features to decrease its error rates is used. The paradigm of autocorrelation (ACR) is to correlate a signal with it itself implying that one segment of the signal is evaluated against shifted versions of itself. The shift amount for each ACR coefficient is proportional to the implied time lag τ .

$$r_t(\tau) = \sum_{j=t+1}^{t+W-\tau} x_j \cdot x_{j+\tau} \quad (3.7)$$

The first ACR coefficient represents the highest peak because it is congruent for both time segments. After an heuristic time threshold the next highest peak represents again a matching of the time segment because of its highest correlation with itself. At the time instant of this peak one pitch period in time got repeated which is the inverse to the underlying fundamental frequency producing one pitch period. All following maximum peaks are repeated versions of the pitch period.

The standard autocorrelation algorithm is prone to errors. Setting time thresholds to apply a frequency range allowing only f_0 's above the lower and below the higher threshold has to be determined heuristically and if set wrong will lead to estimation failures like picking a too high or too low peak. With this, autocorrelation is sensitive for octave and subharmonic errors. Since noise has no harmonic content, the correlation of noise to itself cannot evaluate similarity, thus autocorrelation for f_0 estimation is robust to noise.

Average Magnitude Difference Function (AMDF):

The AMDF algorithm evaluates same as autocorrelation the similarity of a segment against shifted versions of itself, but calculates the difference between two sample values.

$$r_t(\tau) = \sum_{j=t+1}^{t+W-\tau} x_j - x_{j+\tau} \quad (3.8)$$

Instead of a local maximum a local minimum after an heuristic threshold is searched and corresponds to the time period of the estimated f_0 frequency. AMDF shares the same properties like autocorrelation. The algorithm is robust against noise but is prone to pick the wrong minima resulting in octave errors.

Cumulative mean normalized difference function:

In order to improve the selection of one minimum and decrease the error rate, this algorithm divides each lag-value τ by the average of an area around the τ -

coefficient. With this the distance function is normalized and distincts better between lag-instances.

Absolute threshold:

To further decrease the error rate, only peaks below an absolute threshold are searched for the smallest value. If no peak is below the absolute threshold the global minimum is chosen instead. This method reduces too low errors but slightly increases too high errors.

Parabolic interpolation:

To minimize gross errors each local minimum and its direct neighbours are interpolated by a parabola. The abscissa of the parabola is the period estimate.

Best local estimate:

To account for the influence of non-stationary signals and phase differences, a best local estimate around the period estimate is searched which improves the estimation results.

3.3.6.2 Two-way mismatch

The two-way mismatch (TWM) approach proposed by Maher and Beauchamp in 1993 evaluates the supposed to be harmonic spectrum by calculating the frequency differences between each harmonic partial. A harmonic matching method tries to find the harmonic series that best corresponds to the spectral peaks. The detected peaks are compared against possible f_0 candidates.

The Two-Way Mismatch procedure measures the relation of fitted harmonics and calculates an accuracy error for each estimate. Mismatches between generated harmonics and measured partial frequencies are averaged over a fixed subset of available partials. The mismatch error is the discrepancy between measured and predicted sequences of the harmonic partials. The first mismatch is the frequency difference between each partial in the measured sequence and its nearest neighbour in the predicted sequence. The second mismatch is the mismatch between each harmonic in the predicted sequence and its nearest partial neighbour in the measured sequence.

A weighting scheme makes the procedure robust to noise or absence of certain partials. The TWM corrects octave errors by applying a penalty for partials present in the measured but not predicted data and another penalty for partials being predicted in the measured data but which do not occur in the measured sequence. The mismatch error is never zero, a good estimate is provided by error values below five.

3.3.7 Overlapping Partial

3.3.7.1 Overview

Parson investigated in [Parsons, 1976] the treatment of overlapping partials.

Spectral peaks arising from overlapping harmonics can be identified by three criteria:

1. Distance from neighbouring spectral peaks
2. Symmetry of the peak
3. Phase behaviour across the spectral peak

Irresolvable peaks between adjacent harmonics are interpolated in amplitude. With this the treatment of overlapping partials is performed by interpolating the true spectral shape in amplitude and frequency of the sinusoidal component from the nearest non-overlapped harmonic partials of the same note sharing the same amplitude and frequency modulation. This interpolation from the nearest neighbouring harmonics m_l to the left and m_r to the right of to the currently evaluated harmonic partial m is defined by equation 3.9, was introduced in [Parsons, 1976] and adopted from [Every, 2006], with a_m being the amplitude of the harmonic partial m .

$$a_m = \frac{(m_r - m)a_{ml} + (m - m_l)a_{mr}}{m_r - m_l} \quad (3.9)$$

A differentiation is applied between different types of interlaced or overlapped harmonics partials. Every discusses in [Every and Szymanski, 2006] the separation of pitched notes and provides a summary of research how to filter overlapping harmonics. With this the relation in frequency of the overlapping partials plus the occurrence of the length of the overlapping situation for one frequency band determines different mechanisms to be applied to interpolate between overlapping partials. This overview is summarized in table 3.1.

The linear equation method estimates the partials parameters in a LSE sense by linearising the window function into a mixing matrix and to find the parameters for a sinusoidal model S' of amplitude, frequency and phase which best fit to the observed spectrum S . This achieves an optimal solution for stationary signals.

3.3.7.2 Exploit AM beating

Yeh employs in [Yeh, 2008] the AM beating of harmonic partials in a polyphonic environment to examine f_0 saliences for the estimation of the amount of sources. The

Table 3.1: Overlapping partials treatment

Frequency difference	Time span	Treatment
$\Delta < 25Hz$	$> 2periods$	exploit beating
$\Delta < 25Hz$	$< 2periods$	standard amplitude interpolation
$\Delta < 25Hz$		linear + cubic phase multi-frame interpolation
$25Hz < \Delta < 50Hz$		linear equation
$\Delta > 50Hz$		distinct peaks, process separately

partial beating measure is related to the spectral smoothness principle and disturbs a smooth spectral envelope due to overlapping partials. If at least two sinusoidal components exhibit joint periodic fluctuations, beating in temporal envelope by amplitude modulation is introduced. The beating magnitude and the beating with adjacent partials is defined by the sinusoid with the smaller magnitude while the beating rate depends on the frequency difference Δf .

Exploiting the beating of two slowly time-varying harmonics within a certain frequency range obtains the amplitude envelopes of the individual harmonic partials, as explained in [Every and Szymanski, 2006]. The partial with a higher amplitude is computed by low-pass filtering the original envelope of the interlaced components. The sinusoid with the lower amplitude is obtained by subtracting the former result from the original spectrum range, half-wave rectifying and as well low-pass filtering the result. The latter two procedures are employed in [Hu and Wang, 2002] to retrieve the modulation frequency of AM beating.

This method is limited in three aspects:

- Only two overlapping partials can be treated
- Constant amplitude and frequency trajectories for both harmonics are assumed. The method is thus less suited for instruments with AM/FM modulation or vibrato
- A minimum beating duration is required for accurate measure of the beat period, maxima and minima

Two interwoven sinusoids with the amplitudes α_1 and α_2 and with the angular frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 produce one sinusoid of frequency $(\omega_1 + \omega_2)/2$ with an amplitude modulation of $|\omega_2 - \omega_1|/2$. This relation is expressed in equation 3.10.

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 \cdot \cos(\omega_1 t + \Delta\varphi) + \alpha_2 \cdot \cos(\omega_2 t) &= (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) \cdot \cos(\omega_2 t) \dots \\ &+ 2\alpha_1 \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\omega_1 + \omega_2}{2} t + \frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\omega_1 - \omega_2}{2} t + \frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

The second cosine term with the lower frequency generates for small differences between the two oscillators $\omega_1 - \omega_2$ the amplitude modulation of the first term with the higher frequency and creates with this the beating effect. The amount of amplitude change is determined by computing the maximum $|a_1| + |a_2|$ and the minimum $|a_1| - |a_2|$ of the AM envelope.

3.3.7.3 Cubic phase interpolation

The interpolation of phases over frames matches sinusoidal frequencies with smoothness constraints from different frames to a sinusoidal model and applies the cubic phase interpolation function, defined by equation 3.11. The result is a quadratic frequency interpolation, which is employed in [McAulay and Quatieri, 1986] by McAulay and Quatieri.

$$\phi_m(t) = \zeta + \gamma \cdot t + \alpha \cdot t^2 + \beta \cdot t^3 \quad (3.11)$$

3.3.7.4 Spectral shape phase interpolation

In order to recover the phase of one sinusoidal component in an overlapped situation a procedure similar to a non-linear least square methods estimates the phase by considering the frequency and magnitude of all FFT coefficients $F(k)$ describing the pure sinusoid with a set of equations being comprised in matrix U . Inverting the matrix U solves the equation to determine the phase to be interpolated, as expressed in equation 3.12

$$\phi = U^{-1} \cdot \hat{F} \quad (3.12)$$

3.3.7.5 Subtracting filters in signal separation

In [Every and Szymanski, 2006], three different filters are designed to separate overlapping harmonics. The first two filters are energy-based filter designs which partition the energy distribution in a spectral peak region into one part for each harmonic contribution reflecting the predictions for amplitude and frequency and disregarding the phases. The first filter is normalized so that the overlapping filters sum to unity across the peak to filter out the entire peak and the residual. The edges of the second overlapping filters decay according to the shape of the window function applied for the STFT. The third filter approximates the spectral shape of a sum of stationary harmonics with amplitudes a_m , frequencies f_m and phases ϕ_m .

1. Overlapped and normalized filters sum to unity across a spectral peak region

2. Split the energy in an overlapping peak into parts reflecting the amplitude and frequency predictions but neglect phase information
3. Employ sinusoidal modelling to estimate amplitude, frequency and phase of sinusoids and the shape of spectral peaks

The latter method is employed in this research work for estimation but not filtering purposes, despite this third and most complex approach exhibits the following drawbacks:

- Information about the frequency and shape of the spectral peak is not accurate enough
- Partials close in frequency let the linear equation sets become singular
- Different amplitudes of overlapping partials introduce parameter errors

These problems pose one of the main problems for this research work and will be discussed in chapter 4.

3.3.8 Time-frequency representation

The application of the short-time Fourier transformation implies a trade-off between shorter window lengths providing good time but bad spectral resolutions while a longer window lengths provide good spectral but bad temporal resolutions. In order to achieve a compact representation of the analysed polyphonic signal especially for time-modification of audio objects, to achieve higher accuracy in time-varying peak modelling and to achieve a better time-frequency tradeoff the initial usage of successive STFT will be exchanged by one pre-evaluated time-frequency representation. The STFT plus a Gabor transform, a Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), the Constant-Q Transform (CQT), the Multiresolution Fourier transform, the Wigner-Ville time-frequency plane or the Gabor-Wigner distribution are candidates for examination. The latter one is told to discriminate very well polyphonic audio content of separate sources.

Burred reports in [Burred, 2008] that nonuniform-resolution time-frequency representations with frequency-warped filter banks improve the sparsity and with this the separation of sources. Time-frequency representations exhibit frequencies with a good spectral resolution while maintaining a good temporal representation as well but suffer from cross-term interferences. The Wigner-Ville distribution (WVD) has non-negligible interfering crossterms which produces energy in areas where no energy

actually occurs due to smoothing the spectrum. This can be called dark energy, as introduced by Sturm in [Sturm et al., 2008]. On the other hand the WVD provides a very high time and frequency resolutions at the same time and is capable to estimate instantaneous frequencies of harmonic partials within a polyphonic stream, as indicated in [Every, 2006].

Multiresolution time-frequency planes addresses the effect of spectral leakage known from the Fourier transform when one sinusoidal component naturally does not exactly match one frequency bin of the FFT and leaks into the neighbouring bins which as well exhibit correlating energy with the analyzed signal frequency. Windowing a signal segment before a Fourier transformation amplifies this energy leaking. The spectral leakage effect uses the correlation as argument to additionally explain the fact that a frequency residing in the middle of two Fourier coefficients has to raise energy in both bins to avoid quantization errors and to reveal its real nature frequency by interpolation between both magnitudes. The Fourier transform is defined to represent a signal with a finite number of sinus and cosinus functions. The Fourier transform would not be valid if a signal would only stick to one FFT coefficient not representing the real frequency.

In [Levine et al., 1998] different approaches to apply parameter estimation for polyphonic audio content by multiresolution time-frequency representations are evaluated. An octave-spaced wavelet filter bank is used to perform parameter estimation on individual channels which reduces cross-talking and aliasing between channels but is still insufficient for wideband sinusoidal modelling. A parallel bank of constant-Q bandpass filters performs the parameter estimation on bandpass filter outputs well but is highly oversampled and can not be downsampled to reduce the complexity. A multiple sliding FFT is executed with different window lengths per FFT to generate different time-frequency plane resolutions. Finally an octave-spaced, complementary filter bank (CFB) is implemented performing per channel sinusoidal modelling with own windowing and analysis parameters. The CFB approach employs complementary decimation and integration filters which avoids the aliasing cross-talk problem known from the Wavelet filter bank, enables downsampling to be less complex than the constant-Q transform and provides aliasing-free subbands without overlapping.

Another multiresolution approach for note detection in a polyphonic audio environment is proposed by Alonso in [Alonso, 2007] with a Pitch-Synchronous Wavelet Spectrogram (PSWS). A Wavelet-based representation with its intrinsic dyadic frequency tiling decomposes to an octave-based frequency distribution for musical notes which provides not enough resolution to resolve the 12 semitones within every octave. Therefore the Wavelet representation is modified to analyze musical signals with one wavelet per semitone in order to refine the correlation with the fundamental frequency of every note in every octave. The lengths of the Wavelets basis functions ideally coincide with the fundamental periods of a harmonic signals to evaluate the similarity between the analysed signal segment and the chosen basis function. The PSWS raises

a DC pattern for one f_0 and its harmonic partials resulting in a spectrogram-like representation which allows only small tolerance. A DC pattern outside a tolerance interval produces false positives. Variations like the vibrato of a singing voice result in AC patterns and are filtered out. Improving this approach to a higher resolution by for example employing 36 PSWS would match an HPCP-like implementation with a resolution of 1/10 semitone, as introduced in [Gomez, 2006].

Goodwin mentioned already in [Goodwin, 1997] that a correct modification of filter bank coefficients for perfect reconstruction is difficult and proposes thus a hybrid model combining the flexibility of sinusoidal parameters and a representational accuracy with an accurate time-frequency tradeoff.

3.4 Phase Vocoder

In [Flanagan and Golden, 1966], Flanagan and Golden proposed in the year 1966 the phase vocoder, based on the Vocoder (Voice Coder) of Dudley from 1936 which employed an analog bandpass filter bank to retrieve the time-varying spectral energy in each frequency band and to estimate the vocal tract filter. For such an approach, each bandpass filter should not overlap with neighbouring filter channels and be designed with a sharp cut off frequency response.

The phase vocoder interprets the bandpass filter bank in the spectral domain employing a Fourier transform to enable additional phase modulation of complex sinusoids in the synthesis stage while preserving the amplitude envelope like the channel vocoder. The input signal is analyzed and matched as a sum of sine waves with time-varying amplitudes and frequencies to the model for modification before synthesis. One sinusoidal component in each filter bank channel or in several frequency bins is correctly represented while the presence of more sinusoidal components for the computation of the instantaneous amplitude and frequency worsens the results. With the Fourier transform the shape of the bandpass filters and the steepness of their cutoff edges is defined by the shape of the window function used for the STFT. Additive synthesis reconstructs the audio signal using the original amplitude spectrum and its calculated phase-derivative.

Dolson provides in [Dolson, 1986] a comprehensive overview of the phase vocoder for time-scaling or pitch-transposition. The time-varying amplitude and frequency signals for each oscillator are control signals carrying temporal information so that the phase vocoder can separate temporal and spectral information. The phases obtained from the analyzed signal describe the time-varying frequency continuation of the input signal and need to be adopted before re-synthesis to describe the output signal. A possible time-scale factor applied defines the amount of rescaling applied to the phases on the unit circle to introduce the same frequency variation from the analysis into the synthesis stage. Pitch-transposition with the phase vocoder for integer factors

only can be accomplished easily by time-scaling with the desired pitch-change factor and playing back with original sample rate times the applied factor. This retains the original duration but modifies the frequency content.

Miller Puckette introduced in [Puckette, 1995] the phase locking of adjacent frequency bins because a complex sinusoid excites in general several spectral bins. Treating each frequency bin separately deteriorates their relative interrelation to describe the exciting sinusoidal component. Phase locking by using a weighted average of the related phases reduces significantly the reverberation artefacts of the phase vocoder known as phasiness when applied to e.g. time-scaling. Phase locking is also applied to handle transients because of its stochastic behaviour.

3.5 Time-scaling

The stretching or compressing of audio content over time slows down or speeds up the sound. Playing back one audio object with a slower or faster rate leads to the unnatural sounding “munchkinization” effect because the formants are changed simultaneously with the same stretch or compression factor. Expanding audio data in time by playing back slower lowers the pitch while shortening in time by playing back faster increases the pitch. A time-scale algorithm should therefore modify the duration of an audio signal without altering the perceived pitch and timbre by preserving the spectral envelope or time-domain shape of audio segments.

Audio time-scaling in time-domain is based on Synchronized Overlap-and-Add (SOLA) techniques which discard or repeat selected audio segments. Pitch-Synchronous Overlap-and-Add (PSOLA) relies on f_0 information to select time segments corresponding to one pitch period. Waveform Similarity Overlap-and-Add (WSOLA) auto-correlates different time segments to determine one audio segment for the following Overlap-and-Add process with highest similarity. Time-domain methods require quasi-periodic audio content in order to achieve high quality because stochastic noise components exhibit no fundamental frequency for f_0 information nor achieve similarity when being cross-correlated. Polyphonic audio streams are as well less suited for time-domain based time-scaling due to the poor frequency localization while a frequency domain approach suffers from poor time localization.

3.5.1 Vertical and horizontal phase coherence

Frequency-domain approaches for time-scaling audio data employ techniques based on the phase vocoder and sinusoidal modelling but suffer from reverberant artefacts known as “phasiness” due to the loss of the vertical and horizontal phase coherence.

The horizontal phase coherence refers to the synchronization between successive frames and a smooth amplitude and frequency continuation of complex sinusoids de-

scribed in each phase vocoder channel over time. A time-scale or pitch-shift algorithm needs to ensure high similarity between connected frames before an Overlap-and-Add procedure. This horizontal synchronization is maintained by calculating the expected phase of each sinusoidal component in each subband following the simple sinusoidal phase propagation rule which is expressed by equation 3.13 with the sinusoidal frequency component ω , the instantaneous phase ϕ_1 at time t_1 and the expected phase ϕ_2 at time t_2 .

$$\phi_2 = \phi_1 + \omega(t_2 - t_1) \quad (3.13)$$

The vertical phase coherence describes the smooth continuation of true sinusoidal components between the subbands of one frame. Applying the phase propagation rule to spurious peaks of stochastic nature results in the loss of the vertical phase coherence between the phase vocoder channels. A sophisticated distinction between peaks from a true sinusoid and spurious peaks resulting from sidelobes of the windowing process of the STFT, from non-stationary modulations or frequency modulated noise components of coloured noise reduces reverberation but does not maintain the true vertical phase coherence. Time-domain algorithms for time-scaling naturally maintain the vertical phase coherence of the quasi-harmonic phasors of one audio source because the signal is not split into neighbouring subbands and processed in a coherent manner.

3.5.2 Time-scaling with the phase vocoder

Time-scaling in the frequency-domain with phase vocoder techniques is accomplished by segmenting the input and output streams into overlapping analysis and synthesis frames. The hop size for each stream defines the distance to the next windowing position. A varying ratio between the analysis hop size R_a with respect to the resynthesis hop size R_s defines the time scaling factor $\alpha = R_s/R_a$. Time-scale expansion set $R_a < R_s$ to slow down and time-scale compression sets $R_a > R_s$ to speed up the output. In [Barry et al., 2008], fixing the synthesis hop size R_s and varying the analysis hop size R_a avoided amplitude modulation.

Modifying the phase spectrum affects as well the synthesis windowing function which is recommended to be set to $> 75\%$ overlap to avoid modulations and maintain the horizontal phase coherence over time. The synthesis frames are overlapped synchronously with updated coherent phases. The instantaneous frequencies in radians are required to predict the synthesis phases of any spectral component and synthesis hop size. The phase estimates decrease in accuracy with larger hop sizes due to non-stationary short-term signal modulations.

Short-Time Fourier Transform X_k^u :

The STFT for phase vocoder based time-scaling with the analysis window w_a is in-

terpreted in [Derrien, 2007] and expressed by equation 3.14 to overlap two successive analysis frames by $N - R_a$ samples with R_a being the analysis hop size, u the analysis index and k the frequency index for each Vocoder channel.

$$X(k, u) = \sum_{n=0}^N w_a(n) \cdot x(n + uR_a - N/2) \cdot e^{-j2\pi \frac{kn}{N}} \quad (3.14)$$

Phase initialization $\angle Y(t_s^0, \Omega_k)$:

The phases from the analysis frame $\angle X(t_a^0, \Omega_k)$ are copied to the synthesis phase spectrum $\angle Y(t_s^0, \Omega_k)$ for initialization and the following phase increment process starting with the correct phase spectrum.

$$\angle Y(t_s^0, \Omega_k) = \angle X(t_a^0, \Omega_k) \quad (3.15)$$

Phase increment $\Delta\Phi_k^u$:

The phase increment equation 3.16 defines the phase deviation between adjacent analysis frames $t_a^u - t_a^{u-1}$ and the predicted phase difference for bins centre frequency Ω_k over the hop size R_a .

$$\Delta\Phi_k^u = \angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_k) - \angle X(t_a^{u-1}, \Omega_k) - R_a\Omega_k \quad (3.16)$$

The index u denotes the frame number, k the frequency bin, a denotes analysis and later s denotes synthesis.

Phase unwrapping $\Delta_P\Delta\Phi_k^u$:

The principal determination returns the principal argument of the phase for each frame. This unwraps the phase from the modulo 2π representation to its actual value. Additionally the shifting of the spectral representation from the borders of the Fourier transform to the middle accomplishes a more efficient phase relationship, as explained in [de Goetzen et al., 2000].

Instantaneous frequency $\hat{\omega}_k(t_a^u)$:

The instantaneous frequency measured in radians per sample in the analysis frame depends on the phase increment $\Delta_P\Delta\Phi_k^u$ and the the k^{th} bin centre frequency $\Omega_k = 2\pi k/N$, described by equation 3.17.

$$\hat{\omega}_k(t_a^u) = \Omega_k + \frac{\Delta_P\Delta\Phi_k^u}{R_a} \quad (3.17)$$

Phase propagation $\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k)$:

The corresponding phase spectrum for the synthesis frame is calculated by multiplying the instantaneous frequencies computed with 3.17 by the synthesis hop size

R_s and adding the results to the previous synthesis phase spectrum to apply phase propagation, defined by equation 3.18.

$$\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = \angle Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k) + R_s \hat{\omega}_k(t_a^u) \quad (3.18)$$

This advances the phases from the last synthesis frame $\angle Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k)$ to the current synthesis frame $\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k)$ for the duration of R_s and at a rate of the instantaneous frequency $\hat{\omega}_k(t_a^u)$.

Resynthesis $\mathbf{y}(t)$:

The input magnitude spectrum $|X(t_a^u, \Omega_k)|$ of the current analysis frame is copied to the synthesis stage without any transformation applied to it. The propagated output phases $\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k)$ for the current synthesis frame plus the copied magnitudes determine an inverse FFT followed by the same windowing function $w_a(n)$ employed to weight the input data segment to compute the output waveform, as expressed by equation 3.19.

$$y_u(t) = w_a(t) \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |X(t_a^u, \Omega_k)| \cdot e^{\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k)} \quad (3.19)$$

A final Overlap-and-Add process described by equation 3.20 adds the current output frame $y_u(t)$ to the output waveform y .

$$y(t) = \sum_u y_u(t - uR_s + N/2) \quad (3.20)$$

This basic phase vocoder approach maintains the horizontal phase coherence between adjacent frames but suffers from phasiness and the loss of the vertical phase coherence per intra-frame. The loss of the vertical phase coherence originates as well due to wrongly initialized phase values and accumulated phase-unwrapping errors. Setting the synthesis phases at the first evaluated frame to the phases examined in the first analysis frame initially retains the phase coherences but suffers from the loss of vertical phase coherence if the initialization is executed on low-level energy with unrelated sinusoidal components and spurious noise components.

In this scenario the phase unwrapping differences accumulate differently the term $\sum_{i=1}^u 2m_k^i \pi$ in different channels and deteriorate the vertical phase coherence. This term accounts for the phase unwrapping to determine the addition or subtraction of multiples of 2π , as explained in [Laroche, 2003] and [Laroche, 1999]. One wrongly calculated phase-unwrapping factor leads to a biased phase of $2\alpha\pi$ in subsequent frames. Phase-unwrapping errors can be avoided by reconstructing from the STFT magnitude exclusively or by fitting the spectrum to a sum of sinusoids.

3.5.3 Time-scaling with phase locking

The traditional phase vocoder treats in a wrong manner every frequency bin of the Fourier transform as one sinusoidal components and neglects the fact that one sinusoidal component is usually described by several neighbouring frequency bins sharing correlated energy with the excitatory sinusoid. The smooth phase continuation without jumps between the frequency bins for one spectral frame is broken. This problem is addressed by the improved phase vocoder which locks the phases of a spectral region being excited by one sinusoidal component. This retains the local phase relationship for the sinusoid and maintains the vertical phase coherence of the frame. Before the standard phase vocoder applied phase propagation to each single phase and lost the vertical phase coherence. Now the locked phases are jointly updated according to equation 3.18 to maintain the vertical and horizontal phase coherence.

The approach requires the distinction between real and spurious sinusoidal peaks. Frequency bins related to a non-sinusoidal peak Ω_k are updated by retaining the phase relationship to the closest bins of a real sinusoidal component Ω_{kP} measured in the analysis frame. This phase locking improvement is expressed by equation 3.21.

$$\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = \angle Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_{kP}) - (\angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_{kP}) - \angle X(t_a^u - R_s, \Omega_k)) \quad (3.21)$$

3.5.4 Loose phase locking

This method applies a posteriori constraints to the output synthesis phases. Puckette introduced in [Puckette, 1995] this technique which evaluates the synthesis phase of channel k additionally with the phases of the two neighbouring bins instead of exclusively relying on the phase of the complex number $Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k-1})$. This is expressed by equation 3.22 and is listed in this form in [Laroche and Dolson, 1999].

$$Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) + Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k-1}) + Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k+1}) \quad (3.22)$$

If the sinusoidal peak resides closely around channel k the output phase stays fairly changed because the magnitude of the channels k+1 and k-1 exhibit significantly smaller amplitudes. But if channel k has a lower magnitude than one of the neighbouring channels than the phase for channel k is roughly the one of the dominant peak. With this neighbouring bins are phase-locked which augments the output quality of a phase vocoder approach despite the improvements are minor and signal-dependent.

Puckette defines an improved resynthesis formula, like given in equation 3.23.

$$Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = X(t_s^u, \Omega_k) \cdot \left(\frac{Z(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k)}{X(t_s^u, \Omega_k)} \right) \cdot \left| \frac{Z(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k)}{X(t_s^u, \Omega_k)} \right|^{-1}$$

(3.23)

with $Z(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k) = Z(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k) = Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k) - Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_{k-1}) - Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_{k+1})$

3.5.5 Rigid phase locking

The loose phase locking is performed for every channel independently of its content. With this the synthesis phases around one sinusoid change gradually and the vertical phase coherence is developed slowly. Rigid phase locking extends loose phase locking by exclusively considering sinusoids in a peak picking stage for the phase vocoder channels to apply phase propagation.

Peaks are identified if its magnitude is larger than four nearest neighbours. For each peak the surrounding spectral region is phase-locked to the peak phase of the channel. Regions are distinguished by the middle in frequency or the lowest amplitude between two peaks.

3.5.5.1 Identity phase locking

The synthesis phases around one peak are related to the analysis phases by maintaining the phase difference observed in the analysis signal between successive channels to be introduced by similar phase differences in the corresponding synthesis channels.

$$Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k1}) - X(t_a^u, \Omega_k) - X(t_a^u, \Omega_{k1}) \quad (3.24)$$

The dominant peak of the center frequency Ω_{k1} determines equation 3.24.

Identity phase locking performs phase unwrapping only on channels carrying peaks and assures that the instantaneous frequencies of the sinusoids are close to the corresponding channel selected. The phase unwrapping constraint $R_a \cdot \hat{\omega}_h < \pi$ is relaxed to apply larger analysis hop sizes for larger scaling factors. Only channels with peaks require trigonometric calculations. After computing the synthesis phase of one peak channel the angle θ describing the rotation of $X(t_a^u, \Omega_{k1})$ into $Y(t_a^u, \Omega_{k1})$, expressed by equation 3.25.

$$\theta = \angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k1}) - \angle X(t_s^u, \Omega_{k1}) \quad (3.25)$$

The neighbouring channels are computed by employing the phasor $Z = e^{j\theta}$, expressed by equation 3.26.

$$\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = \angle X(t_s^u, \Omega_k) + \theta \quad (3.26)$$

The steps implementing identity phase locking are summarized as follows:

1. Locate prominent peaks in the spectrum
2. Compute the instantaneous frequency using horizontal phase unwrapping
3. Compute the synthesis phases
4. Calculate the rotation angle Φ and phasor Z
5. Rotate all neighbouring channels and their peak region for the current channel

3.5.5.2 Scaled phase locking

Karrer refers in [Karrer et al., 2006] to the proposal of scaled phase locking in [Laroche and Dolson, 1999] which identifies sinusoidal and discards spurious peaks, computes the synthesis phases of these bins and switches the phase vocoder channel if the corresponding sinusoidal component switches as well from channel $k=0$ at frame $u - 1$ to channel $k=1$ at frame u . This assures to select the proper analysis phases to compute the instantaneous frequencies. Equation 3.27 illustrates this possible behaviour and is adopted from equation 3.16.

$$\Delta\Phi_{k1}^u = \angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_{k1}) - \angle X(t_a^{u-1}, \Omega_{k0}) - R_a \Omega_{k1} \quad (3.27)$$

The channel switch needs to be reflected in the computation of the synthesis phase calculation for channel $k1$ and is based on the channel of the previous synthesis frame to follow the sinusoids trajectory. Equation 3.28 expresses this special phase calculation and is derived from equation 3.18.

$$\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k1}) = \angle Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_{k0}) + R_s \hat{\omega}_{k1}(t_a^u) \quad (3.28)$$

The sinusoidal trajectory is determined by selecting the closest peak to channel Ω_{k1} in frame $u - 1$ corresponding best to the peak in channel Ω_{k1} in frame u . The Fourier bins of noise parts not describing a sinusoidal component are phase-locked to the closest peak which is expressed by the phase locking equation 3.29 with a phase scaling factor β .

$$\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = \angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_{k1}) + \beta \|\angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_k) - \angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_{k1})\| \quad (3.29)$$

The phase relations across channels carrying peaks and their neighbouring channels with non-sinusoidal data are transmitted to the appropriate phase vocoder channels in the time-scaled synthesis signal. This preserves the vertical phase coherence especially for sinusoids moving between frequency bins across frames over time. The estimates trajectories might jump across channels for signal parts with less sinusoidal

and more spurious peaks by matching two unrelated peaks which results in a blurred time-scaled output. A sinusoidal trajectory tracking mechanism improves the reliance on frequency distance.

McAulay and Quatieri propose in [McAulay and Quatieri, 1986] to allow only short frequency distances in lower bands and long frequency distances in higher bands.

The steps implementing scaled phase locking are summarized as follows:

1. Locate prominent peaks in the spectrum
2. Locate corresponding peaks in the previous frame
3. Calculate the instantaneous frequencies using horizontal phase unwrapping
4. Calculate the updated synthesis phases
5. Unwrap the analysis phases across all channels

3.5.6 Interpolated phase locking

Bonada proposes in [Bonada, 2002] an interpolation method to minimize phase discontinuities when applying scaled phase-locking which minimizes phasiness. Because of using as well a constant hop size the factor β is not applicable to stretch the time distance for this approach. Scaled phase-locking with $\beta = 1$ equals identity phase-locking plus an additional required peak detection and continuation tracking algorithm.

3.5.7 Time-scaling in real-time

The final implementation in [Barry et al., 2008] is an independent low-latency pitch and time stretching algorithm based on a modified phase vocoder with optional phase locking and transient detection. Real-time issues are discussed where the time-scaling factor α varies instantaneously and introduces artefacts. This is solved by re-defining the time instant position at the analysis stage from $t_a^u = u \cdot R_a$ to $t_a^u = t_a^{u-1} + \alpha R_s$ and by improving the estimation of the instantaneous frequency with the phase differences of the current analysis frame t_a^u and the synthesis frame of one hop size backwards $\angle X(t_a^u - R_s, \Omega_k)$. The selection of the one hop size back synthesis frame avoids phase unwrapping errors, ensures a smooth time-scaling transition but requires an additional FT. This results in an instantaneous phase update equation 3.30 which is derived from the original phase propagation equation 3.18.

$$\angle Y(t_s^u, \Omega_k) = \angle Y(t_s^{u-1}, \Omega_k) + (\angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_k) - \angle X(t_a^u - R_s, \Omega_k)) \quad (3.30)$$

A loss in phase coherence results in amplitude and frequency modulation of the affected sinusoidal components due to the introduced phase differences. The maximum phase tolerance of the human auditory system expresses that amplitude and frequency modulations are inaudible below a certain value, referred to by Dorran in [Dorran et al., 2006]. Here a hybrid time-frequency domain approach tries to unite the advantages of both processing domains. The maximum amplitude, frequency and phase deviation and modulation is considered to push or pull synthesis phases into a horizontal phase coherent state. Having established a horizontal phase coherence the frequency-domain processing is substituted by the deletion and insertion of time-domain segments which in turn establishes vertical phase coherence.

3.5.8 Silent passage phase reset

The phase vocoder algorithm suffers in general from cumulative phase unwrapping errors resulting in the characteristic reverberation artefacts known as phasiness. A solution to this problem is to restore the vertical phase coherence at certain points in the signal continuation when the current energy falls below an heuristic threshold. It is assumed in [Karrer et al., 2006] that low-level energy segments carry no meaningful audible events. The synthesis phases of the time-scaled signal are reset to the phases of the current analysis frame if the energy level exceeds the given threshold. The occurring artefact is almost audible and masked by the rising energy signal. This approach is as well applicable for phase vocoder based pitch-shifting and -scaling techniques.

3.6 Pitch-shifting

Changing the fundamental frequency f_0 of one audio object can be achieved with the three different methods of shifting, scaling or stretching the pitch. The commonly known and utilized name pitch-shifting is not complete in fulfilling the desired task of increasing or decreasing the perceptually interpreted frequency height known as pitch. Shifting all magnitude and maybe its corresponding phase values to other complex FFT bins destroys the harmonic frequency relation between the formerly in an harmonic interval occurring partials. Changing the pitch implies to change as well the frequency distance between harmonic frequency partials by the underlying scaling factor applied. Therefore pitch-shifting refers to the correct denotation if a corresponding pitch-scaling or pitch-stretching algorithm is implied as well, which is the case for this research work.

3.6.1 Pitch-transposition in time domain

The modification of the pitch period or the fundamental frequency f_0 is achieved similarly to time-scale alteration by time-scaling the audio object with the pitch changing factor and sampling the transformed audio object with the new converted sampling rate to retain the original duration. Laroche explains in [Laroche, 1999] that resampling modifies the frequency content as wanted but suffers from the drawback that only linear factors are applicable and therefore restrain this method. For upwards pitch-shifting with a factor $\beta > 1$ the audio input is first re-sampled to a shorter audio signal and then time-scaled to its proper length while downwards pitch-shifting for factors of $\beta < 1$ applies first time-scaling to a smaller duration and resamples afterwards.

Applying seamlessly floating pitch-scaling factors β interpolates or decimates the input time domain signal from t_a^u to $t_a^u + N\beta$. This generates a new analysis frame which as for time-scaling requires a phase update equation calculating the phase propagation for this and all following interpolated frames, as explained in [Barry et al., 2008].

Phase increment $\Delta\Phi_k^u$:

The phase increment equation 3.31 for pitch-scaling estimates the phases for the synthesis frame between the phases of the current analysis frame $\angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_k)$ and the analysis frame one synthesis hop size back $\angle X(t_a^u - R_s, \Omega_k)$.

$$\Delta\Phi_k^u = \angle X(t_a^u, \Omega_k) - \angle X(t_a^u - R_s, \Omega_k) - \left(\frac{1}{\beta} \cdot R_s \Omega_k \right) \quad (3.31)$$

With this the pitch scaling factor β is included in the phase calculation and thus the need to apply time-scaling as first step is omitted.

Instantaneous frequency $\hat{\omega}_k(t_a^u)$:

The instantaneous frequency for pitch-shifting incorporates the phase increment $\Delta\Phi_k^u$, the synthesis hop size R_s and the pitch-scaling factor β and is defined by equation 3.32.

$$\hat{\omega}_k(t_a^u) = \Omega_k + \frac{\beta}{R_s} \cdot \Delta\Phi_k^u \quad (3.32)$$

3.6.2 Pitch-transposition in frequency domain

Instead of achieving pitch-scale modifications by a combination of a time-scaling and a sampling rate conversion process, the direct manipulation of the signals distribution in the frequency-domain allows simple peak picking and shifting. Sinusoidal peaks and their spectral neighbouring region in the magnitude spectrum are shifted to new frequency locations, the corresponding phase-locked phases are adjusted to maintain

the vertical and horizontal phase coherence and the continuity in the phase spectrum, as explained in [Laroche, 1999].

Applying a frequency shift $\Delta\omega$ with a pitch modification factor α in time domain is as introduction defined by equation 3.33.

$$x'(t') = \sum_{i=1}^{I(t')} A_i(t') \exp(j\phi'_i(t')) \quad (3.33)$$

$$\text{with } \phi'_i(t') = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \alpha(\tau) \omega_i(\tau) d\tau$$

Preserving the spectral region while pitch-shifting sinusoidal peaks with its relative amplitude and phase values corresponds in time-domain to the same sinusoid at a different frequency rate. A complex sinusoid with frequency ω is described by $x(n) = A \cdot \exp(j\omega n + j\phi)$ in the time domain and with the STFT described in equation 3.34 at time t_a^u and frequency Ω . $H(\Omega)$ is the Fourier transform of the analysis window $h(n)$ at frequency Ω .

$$X(t_a^u, \Omega_k) = AH(\Omega_k - \omega) e^{j\phi} \quad (3.34)$$

A shift in frequency $\Delta\omega$ around frequency ω of the input signal results in a synthesis signal $Y(t_s^u, \Omega) = X(t_a^u, \Omega - \Delta\omega)$ and an output waveform defined by equation 3.35.

$$y_u(n) = h(n) A e^{j\phi} e^{j(\omega + \Delta\omega)n} \quad (3.35)$$

The peaks phases need to be consistent over frames to ensure horizontal phase coherence. Since the frequency changed from ω to $\omega + \Delta\omega$, the peaks phases have to be rotated by $\Delta\omega R$ or $Z = e^{j\Delta\omega R}$ on the unit circle with R being the hop size. This approach shifts all frequencies by the same amount of $\Delta\omega$. The phase continuity in the analysis is preserved in the synthesis stage if peaks of a region are rotated by the same angle. This behaves similar to phase locking reducing the reverberation artefacts of the phase vocoder.

If shifted spectral regions leak into the negative frequency part the energy is reflected back into the positive frequency region with complex conjugation. Since the shifted sinusoidal frequency resides in most cases naturally on a sub-bin level, frequency-domain interpolation is required. This in turn introduces sinusoidal amplitude modulation in the time-domain which can be reduced by employing an high overlap-factor. Linear interpolation requires at least $> 75\%$ overlap in order to decrease influence from sidebands.

3.6.3 Pitch-transposition with formant preservation

Laroche explains in [Laroche, 2003] a method to shift the spectral locations of harmonic partials and/or individual harmonics. The harmonic phases are updated to reduce or eliminate artefacts and achieves with this time-domain shape-invariance. Important for this work is the spectral envelope estimation and preservation by updating the amplitudes of frequency-changed spectral peaks. This introduces artefacts like noise bursts and loss of clarity when low-energy frequency areas are amplified to preserve the formant structure.

The paradigms called Harmonic Assignment and Harmonic Generation introduces a formant-preserving pitch-modification method. The harmonic partial locations in the spectrum for a pitch-scaling factor α lie at multiples of $\alpha \cdot \omega_{out}$. Individual harmonic regions from the analysis frame being closest to the new peak locations are copied and pasted. This has the advantage that harmonic peaks are employed sharing a similar magnitude than the local spectral envelope. No direct one-to-one mapping of spectral peaks is applied. One harmonic region may be selected for several output harmonics. Harmonic generation interpolates the pasted spectral regions to spectrum coefficients and suffers from synthesis harmonics being generated over frames from different analysis harmonic when changing the pitch-scale factor between frames.

Shape invariance or the concept of phase coherence is related to the relative phases and amplitudes at the pulse onset time of sharp excitation pulses at every pitch period when the shape of the time-domain signal around the pulse onset is roughly independent of the pitch. The measured impulse response origins from the excited vocal tract being the resonant filter.

The definition of pitch-synchronous input and output onset times is a shape-invariant technique to reproduce at the output onset times the phase relationships observed at input onset times. The input and output onset times are updated by $2\pi/\omega_0$ representing the pitch period by the following recursive equations 3.36 and 3.37 with an initialization of the first output onset time instant to the first input onset time $t_0^o = t_0^i$ at the beginning.

$$t_n^i = t_{n-1}^i + \frac{2\pi}{\omega_0} \quad (3.36)$$

$$t_n^o = t_{n-1}^o + \frac{2\pi}{\alpha\omega_0} \quad (3.37)$$

The synthesis phases are set to the analysis phases at same time instants. Since phases can only be measured at analysis frames t_a^u , the closest input and output onset times at time interval t_a^u are considered by incorporating the instantaneous frequency and neighbouring bins of an harmonic partial to set the proper phases in the output spectrum. Equations 3.38 and 3.39 set the relation of the input onset time instant t_n^i and the output onset time instant t_n^o to be closest to t_a^u , the only possible phase

measure with the STFT from the input signal.

$$\phi^i(t_a^u) = \phi^i(t_n^i) + \omega_i(t_a^u - t_n^i) \quad (3.38)$$

$$\phi^o(t_a^u) = \phi^o(t_n^o) + \omega_o(t_a^u - t_n^o) \quad (3.39)$$

In order to ensure that the phase of the output spectra ϕ^o at the output pulse onset time instant t_n^o equals its corresponding input phase ϕ^i at the input pulse onset time instant t_n^i , equation 3.40 adds to the phase $\phi^i(t_a^u)$ measured from the input signal the relation between the frequency at the input ω_i being closest to its input onset t_n^i and at the output frequency ω_o being closest to its output onset t_n^o .

$$\phi^o(t_a^u) = \phi^i(t_a^u) + \omega_o(t_a^u - t_n^o) - \omega_i(t_a^u - t_n^i) \quad (3.40)$$

The addition of the output instantaneous frequency ω_o at frame t_a^u and the subtraction of the instantaneous frequency ω_i at the same frame t_a^u is as well expressed by equation 3.41, which implies the rotation of the phasors through a multiplication with the complex number z .

$$z = e^{j\omega_o(t_a^u - t_n^o) - j\omega_i(t_a^u - t_n^i)} \quad (3.41)$$

This rotates all input phasor bins of harmonic sinusoids by the complex value z on the unit circle requiring only a minimum phase computation without computations for arc tangent, phase unwrapping or interpolation.

Roebel and Rodet apply in [Roebel and Rodet, 2005] the true spectral envelope estimation paradigm to pitch shifting while preserving the spectral envelope to maintain the shape of the vocal tract and with this perceived sound character being processed. Each STFT frame is pre-warped by a simple amplitude multiplication of the amplitude envelope $A(k)$ by a pre-warping factor $P(k)$ in order to compensate for the transposition of the spectral envelope along with the applied pitch scaling factor f , expressed by equation 3.42.

$$P(k) = \frac{A(k \cdot f)}{A(k)} \quad (3.42)$$

This approach suffers when processing high-pitched sounds because the cepstral order of the true envelope estimation needs to be adjusted to fit the highest fundamental frequency f_0 . Thus pre-warping is not applied to frequency regions below and around the first harmonic partial corresponding to f_0 and starts with the second or higher harmonic partials in order to maintain the magnitude of the f_0 partial and to move a possible first formant synchronously with the pitch. This is expressed by equation 3.43 with T_k being the transition bandwidth and k_0 the f_0 bin position.

$$P(k) = \frac{A(k(D(k) + (1 - D(k))f))}{A(k)} \tag{3.43}$$

$$\text{with } D(k) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp((k - k_0)/T_k)}$$

3.7 Multiresolution time- and pitch-scaling

A frequency-dependant peak detection approximates the phase vocoder technique to the non-uniform characteristic of the human auditory system, avoids the modelling of different sinusoids independently in higher frequency bands when being perceived as one component and models on the other hand peaks in lower frequency bands independently, as explained in [Karrer et al., 2006]. A similar approach is taken in [Garas and Sommen, 1998] by utilizing a constant-Q phase vocoder for time- and pitch-scaling.

Chapter 4

Harmonic Audio Object Processing

It occurred to me by intuition, and music was the driving force behind that intuition. My discovery was the result of musical perception - Albert Einstein (when being asked how he got the idea for his theory of relativity)

4.1 Exclusions

To process harmonic audio objects within a polyphonic environment while relying on f_0 and timing information from a MIDI file would in a sophisticated system additionally address possible improvements in order to achieve an highly accurate output signal.

- Voiced / Non-voiced distinction: The discrimination between voiced segments of sinusoidal and non-voiced segments of stochastic noise components augments the transformation quality since quasi-harmonic sinusoidal data is better suited for transformation and high accuracy.
- Instrument modelling: The training of HMMs for different instrument types and classes to describe note events steering a note sequence estimation process for multiple f_0 estimation is employed by Klapuri in [Ryynnen and Klapuri, 2005]. The HMMs build an acoustic model with note model parameters representing the characteristic behaviour of the harmonic partials for different notes. Such a model could be employed for this research approach to approximate the peak detection and estimation algorithm to the harmonic partials amplitude and frequency trajectories. Despite interesting, this is omitted due to a certain expectation of improvement in accuracy while having to put effort in building an acoustic model for different instrument types and classes and as well for different f_0 values and note durations.

- Glissando / Portamento: The test of music containing one or several sound sources which shift its fundamental frequency gradually up or down over time is omitted due to its known peculiarities posing technical problems for this research approach.

4.2 System

The transformation of spectral peaks p_k and its surrounding bins n as interpreted in [Loscos, 2007] with Spectral Peak Processing based on rigid phase locking techniques might be less applicable for processing polyphonic audio content. Despite we choose this technique because of employing setups with low polyphony and aim to detect and resolve overlapping partials. Interlaced and overlapped harmonic partials within one frequency region or band are treated by interpolating them to their ideally true spectral shape of sinusoids, defined in the time domain by $s_t = a_t \cdot \cos(\omega_t t + \theta_t)$ with the instantaneous amplitude a_t , angular frequency ω_t and phase θ_t . The approximation process loses information which will be measured by objective evaluation algorithms and evaluated by a final subjective listening test. Stochastic components like transients are addressed as well, despite the modelling of the residual is skipped due to time limitations for a corresponding implementation.

The transformation process to a new time-frequency plane and the synthesis to a waveform output is executed by the following steps.

1. Detect and interpolate peaks in the spectrum
2. Match peaks within a frequency range to the a priori f_0 and timing information
3. Discriminate between transient, overlapped or pure sinusoidal peak regions
4. Model transients peak-wise, copy their magnitude contour to the new TF plane and re-initialize their phases
5. Copy pure sinusoidal peak regions to the new TF plane
6. Treat overlapped peak regions accordingly before placing them onto the new TF plane
7. Iteratively transform the new TF plane plus apply note transformation like time-scaling or pitch-transposition
8. Re-synthesize to an output stream using overlap-add

4.3 STFT techniques

This chapter explains several paradigms employed with the usage of a Fourier transform along with windowed audio segments, commonly known as short-time Fourier transform (STFT).

4.3.1 Windowing

Choosing a window type is always a trade-off between the width of the main-lobe B_s , the maximum side-lobe height and the side-lobe decay, expressed in dB per octave. The window $w(t)$ chosen to weight each input and output segment of audio samples is of type Blackman-Harris because of being well-suited for audio processing tasks due to its low side-lobe magnitudes and high decay of the side-lobes, despite its main-lobe width is not as narrow as e.g. the main-lobe of a rectangular window. We choose an odd-length window size of $M=2061$ comprising 46.72 milliseconds of audio data.

The window size is chosen according to the lowest fundamental frequency of $f_0 = 97$ Hz occurring in the tests. The size of half the main-lobe B_s of a Blackman-Harris window with 92 dB side-lobe attenuation in DFT bins is 4.2, resulting in a total of 9 bins. This size is independent of the utilized sizes of Fourier transform size N and hop size R between each analysis point in time. With this a minimum size for the required window size of length M can be calculated.

When a window $w(t)$ is convoluted with a time domain signal $x(t)$ before a DFT is executed in order to avoid discontinuities in the resulting spectrum, it expresses that the frequency response $W(t)$ of the window type is shifted by the frequency ω of the analyzed time domain signal $x(t)$ to its corresponding frequency location $X(\omega_k)$ in the spectrum X . In order to resolve two frequencies f_1 and f_2 of two different sinusoids s_1 and s_2 , the required mainlobe bandwidth B_f has to be smaller than the frequency difference δf in Hz of both sinusoids. The required minimum window length M_{min} incorporating sufficient sample values $x(t)$ of both underlying pitch periods $T_1 = 1/f_1$ and $T_2 = 1/f_2$ is calculated using equation 4.1, with B_s being the main-lobe bandwidth in samples and f_s being the sampling rate, as introduced in [Serra, 1989].

$$M \geq B_s \cdot \frac{f_s}{\Delta f} \quad (4.1)$$

In order to resolve the spectral peaks $p_n \forall P \in X$ corresponding to the harmonic frequency partials h_p of a harmonic audio signal $x(t)$, the required minimum frequency difference δf_{min} reduces to the fundamental frequency f_0 which defines the difference in frequency between adjacent harmonic partials h_p and h_{p+1} . The bandwidth value B_s describes how many pitch periods have to be used in the analysis stage in order to resolve spectral peaks accurate enough.

$$M \geq B_s \cdot \frac{f_s}{f_0} \quad (4.2)$$

We determine the minimum window size M_{min} in samples through the following calculation.

$$M \geq B_s \cdot \frac{f_s}{f_0} \geq 4.2 \cdot \frac{44100Hz}{97} = 1909.5 \quad (4.3)$$

We add a security margin of 152 samples and employ the mentioned window size of $M=2061$ in all tests. The initial older implementation used the following Matlab code.

```

1 % Blackman-Harris 92 dB
2 winold = zeros(M,1);
3 fConst = 2*pi/M;
4 w1 = (1:M)';
5 winold = .35875 -.48829*cos(fConst*w1)+.14128*cos(fConst*2*w1) ...
6          -.01168*cos(fConst*3*w1);

```

This produced a symmetric but also even window which did not center the window at exactly the middle bin and did not produce exact half-lag windows at the left and right side, as illustrated by the following check in Matlab.

```

1 len=length(winold);
2 winold(round(len/2)-3:round(len/2)+3)
3
4 ans =
5     0.99997
6     0.99999
7         1
8         1
9     0.99999
10    0.99997
11    0.99993

```

Employing simply the Matlab build-in function `blackmanharris(M)` with the window size M as argument avoids this error.

```

1 win = zeros(M,1);
2 win = blackmanharris(M);
3 win(round(len/2)-3:round(len/2)+3)
4
5 ans =

```

6	0.99995
7	0.99998
8	0.99999
9	1
10	0.99999
11	0.99998
12	0.99995

This provides an odd-length window which can be centered around its middle sample.

4.3.2 Zero-padding

Zero-padding is required to zero-pad the windowed and to be analysed audio segment of any arbitrary length up to the next higher power of two in order to be able to employ a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Zero-padding in the time domain gives an ideal interpolation in the frequency domain, improves the quality of spectral displays and oversamples spectral peaks p_k so that a simple peak interpolation is accurate enough. The modification of a signal in the spectral domain alters its length in the time domain. Thus it is necessary when applying spectral modifications with a STFT approach to employ zero-padding in order to avoid aliasing artefacts when reconstructing the time domain signal from a modified Fourier transform.

We employ a window of odd-length $M=2061$ along with a DFT size of $N=4096$, leading to a zero-padding factor of $N/M = 4096/2061 = 1.9874$.

4.3.3 Zero-phase windowing

The usual zero-padding appends zeros to the right end of the windowed input signal in the FFT input buffer and introduces a time-offset as a complex exponential factor in the phase spectrum. A constant phase spectrum $\Theta_{1...N}$ where the signals' phases θ_k aren't modified by the windowing process is achieved through zero-phase windowing which shifts the halves of the windowed signal to the left and right side of the FFT input buffer and zero-pads in the middle. This centers the signal at time zero because the centre of the analysis window is placed at the first instead of the middle sample of the FFT input buffer. This results in less frequency jitter, a constant horizontal phase continuation for the duration of a quasi-stationary sinusoids main-lobe as well as in less spectral smearing because the linear phase trend being usually introduced by the analysis window is removed.

An example implementation of zero-phase windowing is given by the following Matlab code.

```

1 % analysis
2 winsig = x(pin+1:pin+M) .* win(1:M);
3 fftbuffer(1:(M+1)/2) = winsig((M+1)/2:M);
4 fftbuffer(N-(M-1)/2:N) = winsig(1:(M-1)/2);
5
6 % synthesis
7 realsig((M+1)/2:M) = fftbuffer(1:(M+1)/2);
8 realsig(1:(M-1)/2) = fftbuffer(N-(M-1)/2:N);

```

According to [Serra, 1989] or [Smith, 2007b], the second half $((M+1)/2:M)$ of the windowed signal `winsig` represents the positive time segment to be stored at the beginning of the FFT input buffer while the first half $(1:(M-1)/2)$ of `winsig` represents the negative time segment which is stored at the end of the FFT input buffer. Figure 4.1 shows the standard windowing technique in the subplot above and zero-phase windowing with zero-padding in the subplot below by windowing a synthetic sinusoid of 220 Hz.

Figure 4.1: Standard (above) and zero-phase (below) windowing

Additionally we center each frame in the analysis and synthesis stage around time instant zero instead of starting from time instant zero and continuing to the right. This is a similar approach to the Maximally Flat Phase Alignment (MFPA) employed in [Bonada, 2008], with the difference that in a polyphonic environment we would receive several candidates with lowest phase difference. Therefore we set an arbitrary pulse onset time instant at time zero to synchronize harmonic partials as much as possible in order to receive a flat phase spectrum by centering the analysis window and to avoid linear phase shifts of $e^{-j\omega\Delta t}$ along the frequency axis.

4.3.4 Frequency domain handling

The implemented software system in Matlab employs a logarithmic frequency scale for all signal relevant executions throughout this thesis, despite a linear scale is as well implemented for test purposes. The phase spectrum for the employed Phase Vocoder technique for time-scaling and pitch-transposition does not require phase unwrapping at the Fourier transformation stage.

```
1 X = fft(fftbuffer);
2 if linear > 0
3     magX = abs(X);
4 else
5     magX = 20*log10(abs(X));
6 end
7 phaX = angle(X);
8
9 % ...
10 % execute spectral processing algorithms
11 % ...
12
13 % polar to rectangular coordinates
14 if linear > 0
15     Xnew = magX .* exp(j.*phaX);
16 else
17     linmagX = 10 .^(magX/20);
18     Xnew = linmagX .* exp(j.*phaX);
19 end
```

All processing in the frequency domain is executed on the positive frequency side while the negative frequency representation is set to zero. We mirror the positive to the negative frequency side before the reconstruction to the time domain with the inverse Fourier transform.

```
1 % mirror positive to negative frequency side
2 Xnew(N2+1:N, frame) = conj(flipud(Xnew(2:N2+1, frame)));
```

4.3.5 Perfect reconstruction

Window Energy Correction:

The employed Blackman-Harris window $w(t)$ as explained and employed in chapter 4.3.1 exhibits an energy contour from zero to one which would add energy in dependence of the window length M to the analysed signal $x(t)$ to be transformed.

This can be avoided by normalizing the windows energy to add up to one over its integral contour through dividing each sample by the overall sum of the window $\sum_1^M w(t)$.

```

1 % standard window
2 win = zeros(M,1);
3 win = blackmanharris(M);
4
5 % window with corrected energy
6 win = win ./ sum(win);

```

Figure 4.2 illustrates this behaviour before the energy correction in the subplot above and after the energy correction in the subplot below when checking their amplitude scale.

Figure 4.2: Standard window (above) and window with corrected energy (below)

Overlap-Add Energy Correction:

In [de Goetzen et al., 2000] the effect of the overlap-add process on the energy of the output signal $y(t)$ in dependence to the synthesis hop size R is explained, along with a perfect reconstruction approach by multiplying the analysis with the tapering window $w_{tap}(t)$, scaling the multiplication result by R and dividing this result from the output signal $y(t)$.

Similarly we first avoid the usage of a tapering window $w_{tap}(t)$ at the synthesis stage when reconstructing the output signal $y(t)$ via an overlap-add process. But

we add up a tapering window $w_{tap}(t)$ simultaneously to a parallel 'envelope' signal $y_{env}(t)$ in order to account for the windows energy portion per synthesis frame in dependence of the synthesis hop size R_s directly. With this we do not have to divide the reconstructed output signal $y(t)$ by a single constant but execute an exact sample-by-sample division for perfect reconstruction.

Window tapering is the multiplication of the samples in the output buffer for each frame before the actual overlap-add process with the same window $w(t)$ applied in the analysis stage in order to avoid phase discontinuities at the beginning and at the end of one frame. The overlap-add process for this audio processing approach cannot provide an identity operation by summing up all windows applied in the analysis and synthesis stage to a constant due to the modification of the phases in the transformation stage.

```

1 % accumulation of the 'envelope' signal tfoutenv
2 % in the synthesis overlap-add process
3 tfoutenv(pout+1:pout+M) = tfoutenv(pout+1:pout+M) + win(1:M);
4 % subtraction after the synthesis overlap-add process
5 tfout = tfout ./ tfoutenv;

```

The exemplification code shown does not account for the centering of each synthesis frame around the output pointer `pout`.

4.4 Overlapping Partial Treatment

4.4.1 Overlapping Partial Analysis

Before the implementation and execution of algorithms dealing with sinusoids s_p we want to analyse different behaviours which may occur in this environment so that sinusoids s_p being close in frequency ω and thus influencing each other will not introduce artefacts while a later processing of the audio content with our Phase Vocoder approach. Therefore we employ pure sinusoidal tones instead of real music signals in order to avoid wrong assumptions.

4.4.2 Interlaced partials

In order to analyse and validate our approach of how to treat overlapping partials precisely we initially set up a clean environment by generating two monophonic signals $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ with the fundamental frequencies of $f_{0_1} = 75$ Hz and $f_{0_2} = 175$ Hz. We generate for each track pure sinusoidal tones s_p for the first five harmonic partials. We mix both streams together and provide to the algorithm a single-channel

polyphonic stream with frequencies at 75 Hz, 150 Hz, 225 Hz, 300 Hz and 375 for f_{01} and 175 Hz, 350 Hz, 525 Hz, 700 Hz and 875 Hz for f_{02} . With this we examine the behaviour of tangent but not exactly overlapped partials. We identify two regions of interest. The first region includes a frequency difference of 25 Hz for partial two of f_{01} at 150 Hz and partial one of f_{02} at 175 Hz and another frequency difference of 50 Hz between partial one of f_{01} and partial three of f_{01} at 225 Hz. The second region includes a frequency difference of 50 Hz for partial four of f_{01} at 300 Hz and partial two of f_{02} at 350 Hz and another frequency difference of 25 Hz between partial five of f_{01} at 375 Hz and again partial two of f_{01} . Figure 4.3 shows the plot from Matlab for this setup. The vertical lines depict for f_{01} in red and f_{02} in green the theoretical frequency location of the generated sinusoids s_p and do not reflect the frequencies f_{iploc} retrieved from the signal $x(t)$ by the interpolation algorithm in the spectrum X .

Figure 4.3: Example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 175 Hz with five partials each

From the plot we see immediately the properties and/or problems of our chosen environment. Only the 5th partial of f_{02} exemplifies at its right side very nice the highest side-lobe of the Blackman-Harris window at -92 dB because of not being influenced by the energy of other adjacent sinusoids. No valleys until the first side-lobes can be observed at spectral regions where the frequency partials h_p reside more closely together, also because as already explained the main-lobe bandwidth B_s of the Blackman-Harris window is relatively broad.

More important for this research work is the behaviour at overlapping partials o_p . In our example of two f_0 tracks $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$ with five partials each and the fundamental frequencies of 75 and 175 Hz the peak interpolation algorithm provides peaks for the current frame example at the frequencies 75 Hz, 160 Hz, 229 Hz, 295 Hz,

363 Hz, 525 Hz, 700 Hz and 875 Hz. The harmonic partials for f_{0_1} clearly match the expected harmonic frequencies for the partials one, three and four at the frequencies 75 Hz, 229 Hz and 295 Hz and are true sinusoidal peaks resulting exclusively from this monophonic track. The harmonic partials for f_{0_2} and their harmonic partials three, four and five are as well not overlapped, which leads to the apparent conclusion that partial two at 150 Hz from f_{0_1} is overlapped with partial one at 175 Hz from f_{0_2} and both result in one single peak at 160 Hz. The same assumption is valid for partial five at 375 Hz from f_{0_1} and its overlapped partner partial two at 350 Hz from f_{0_2} , resulting as well in one single peak p_k at 363 Hz. The fusion of overlapping partials is explained in detail in [Bonada, 2008].

A simple peak picking and matching algorithm would with this assign in a wrong manner each overlapped peak to both monophonic tracks with their corresponding fundamental frequencies because of having to allow a natural deviation from the pure integer harmonic frequencies in order to account for the slightly inharmonic nature of musical instruments. Therefore we come to a **first assumption** that checking for two spectral peaks p_k and p_{k+1} within a narrow-band does not necessarily identify overlapping partials o_p . This first assumption might lead to a hypothesis claiming that the existence of one spectral peak can comprise several sinusoidal components within its frequency boundaries.

Figure 4.4: 2D spectrogram of one second for the example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 175 Hz

To investigate this behaviour deeper we provide a spectrogram plot of a longer time duration for this test setup in figure 4.4. Here we examine a small but clear distinction of both 'overlapping' or to be more precise adjacent and mutual influencing

frequency regions. We could now change the parameters of our STFT environment by for example incrementing the zero-padding factor in order to possibly retrieve two distinct peaks in the corresponding narrow-bands. But this would just shortcut the problem temporarily and not lead to the solution we want to achieve, a high qualitative detection and separation of overlapping partials from different monophonic sources. We check further if the behaviour for this example remains constant over frames.

Figure 4.5: Second example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 175 Hz with five partials each

Just one frame in time further we find another behaviour in both interlaced frequency regions, depicted in figure 4.5. First we note that for better viewing purposes we omitted the scaling of the spectrum to 0 dB and plot only down to -50 dB. The interpolation function finds for this frame peaks at the frequencies 75 Hz, 164 Hz, 361 Hz, 525 Hz, 700 Hz and 875 Hz. The behaviour at both tangent frequency regions is the same as in the previous example. The partial two at 150 Hz from f_{0_1} is overlapped with partial one at 175 Hz from f_{0_2} and both result in one single peak at 160 Hz. The partial five at 375 Hz from f_{0_1} is overlapped with partial two at 350 Hz from f_{0_2} and both result in one single peak at 363 Hz. But two partials from f_{0_1} , partial three at 225 Hz and partial four at 300 Hz, are not detected as peaks because the side of the sinusoids main-lobe being adjacent to the interlaced frequency region is correlated with the energy of the corresponding sinusoid of the other monophonic track $x_2(t)$ of f_{0_2} . No DFT bin k of lower energy than the actual maximum can be found and therefore no peak can be detected.

In this case we cannot rely on a peak detection algorithm to pick the closest occurring peak according to the theoretical frequency position of the partial. It would

assign the complete frequency region for the three occurring partials to each partial. Processing such a wrongly detected frequency region with our Phase Vocoder approach would clearly introduce failures in form of artefacts being perceptually relevant. We come to a **second assumption** that we have to implement an algorithm which extends a basic peak picking and matching algorithm by identifying such situations where a sinusoidal component is only half-way visible and does therefore not fulfill the criteria for a peak, that one DFT bin k has a higher magnitude $|X(k)|$ than its left and right neighbour. Additionally we have to investigate after the detection of this situation how we extrapolate the correlated main-lobe side. A simple mirroring of the non-correlated to the correlated main-lobe side might be sufficient. As well we note that the magnitudes of and around $|X(15)|$ and $|X(34)|$ of the overlapped regions at 164 Hz and 361 Hz exemplify an approximately 6 dB higher magnitude value than the non-overlapped sinusoids. Therefore we have to address a change in the magnitude $|X|$ of correlated sinusoids as well, which is our **third assumption**.

We realize that even a pure synthetic signal with constant partial frequencies introduces to our STFT approach different situations when advancing per frame in time. This is not the result of a failure in the STFT setup but clearly the behaviour of AM beating indicated in chapter 3.3.7.2. We continue to examine this test for further different situations to be possibly appearing and think about how to deal with all different frequency measures per STFT frame.

Figure 4.6: Third example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 175 Hz with five partials each

We find another situation, illustrated in figure 4.6, which exhibits a nearly opposite behaviour than the previously analysed second hypothetical situation. Instead of an increase we realize a decrease in magnitude $|X(k)|$ of around -4 dB for the interlaced

regions due to AM beating. The partials one, three and four for f_{0_1} and the partials three, four and five for f_{0_2} reside at their expected frequency position which could give an additional information about the influence of other sinusoids for sounds with no vibrato and instrument types with no or very low harmonic deviation properties. But the partials three and four for f_{0_1} exhibit a broader main-lobe contour than for example partial one of f_{0_1} or the partials three to five for f_{0_2} due to its correlation with the partials one and two from f_{0_2} . Thus part of its energy has to be assigned to the other partials of the tangent sinusoids t_p of the corresponding frequency region, especially due to their lower than usual magnitude $|X(k)|$ for this frame. A nearest neighbour interpolation, as defined in equation 3.9, from non-overlapping or non-interlaced partials from one peak being lower in frequency to the left and from one peak being higher in frequency to the right is feasible for partial two of f_{0_1} by employing the partials one and three. Since partial five does not have a neighbour being higher in frequency this interpolation cannot be employed. But instead, similar to the paradigm of Harmonic Assignment when employing pitch transposition as explained in chapter 3.6.3, we could assign any nearby non-interlaced and non-overlapped partial of the same monophonic track to partial five of f_{0_1} . We just have to assure not to introduce with this a too big amount of magnitude difference when employing another spectral peak region. Therefore the utilization of the nearest neighbour interpolation should be favoured as primer overlapping treatment if feasible, since in our current frame example the magnitude $|X(k)|$ measured is lower than its actual one due to AM beating.

Additionally we note that a standard peak picking and matching algorithm would employ the peak at 142 Hz as valid peak p_2 for partial two of f_{0_1} and accept the frequency difference from its actually pure integer harmonic frequency of 150 Hz as natural harmonic deviation. With our knowledge from the f_0 score for each track about the presence of the first partial of f_{0_2} at 175 Hz we should not accept this frequency deviation Δf . The same statement is valid for partial five of f_{0_1} which has a measured peak p_5 at 384 Hz, should actually exhibit a peak at exactly 375 Hz but is altered in its magnitude value $|X(k)|$ and frequency position k to the influence of partial two of f_{0_2} at 350 Hz. Our **fourth assumption** is that we have to deal with a tradeoff between the fact that beating in interlaced frequency regions alters the true frequency position of sinusoidal peaks p_k but when we will switch to signals from music instruments such a deviation Δf from the theoretical harmonic frequencies of h_p is natural. We call this observation FM beating, despite it is actually a modulation of the phases, as explained for example in [Smith, 2007a]. We note that there is strictly speaking no such a thing as 'FM beating', which suddenly appears for the measure of one frame within the context of AM beating producing a continuous modulation of the magnitude measured in the spectral domain. It appears as 'FM beating' in the magnitude spectrum due to the change of the AM envelope trajectory along with a change in its phase continuation. Despite we have to deal with the 'FM beating' effect in this context and keep therefore this naming convention.

The hardest problem to solve for the situation exemplified at this frame is that no peaks exists for the first two partials of f_{0_2} . The only solution is to insert at the corresponding frequency positions k the nearest non-overlapped and non-interlaced peak from the same source, which is partial three for both first partials of f_{0_2} . Care has to be taken in the later real world tests with real musical content where over a larger frequency distance no non-overlapped or non-interlaced is available and with this less information is available about the magnitude value $|X(k)|$ required to treat the current peak. Instead of looking at partials within the same frame the nearest neighbour interpolation might be feasible to be employed for the same partial p over different previous and following frames. If only two sinusoids s_p would influence each other within a limited frequency region the utilization of the AM beating approach should be preferred. The **fifth assumption** is the requirement of an harmonic partial insertion algorithm for frames where nearest neighbour interpolation is not feasible. Additionally the utilization of a nearest neighbour interpolation for the same harmonic partial over frames is an option.

4.4.2.1 Interlaced and overlapped partials

In order to examine the behaviour if two sinusoidal tones from two different sources not just share tangent partials t_p but also overlapping partials o_p , we set up another synthetic test with two fundamental frequencies at 75 Hz and 100 Hz. We generate frequencies at 75 Hz, 150 Hz, 225 Hz, 300 Hz and 375 for f_{0_1} and 100 Hz, 200 Hz, 300 Hz, 400 Hz and 500 Hz for f_{0_2} . With this we test two exactly overlapping partials at 300 Hz. Additionally we keep an eye on frequency regions with tangent sinusoids t_p being closer than less than or equal 50 Hz in order to validate the observations and possible hypothesis retrieved from the previous test setup. We identify one big frequency region with a sequence of tangent tones from 75 Hz until 225 Hz and frequency differences Δf of 25 or 50 Hz from the partials one, two and three of f_{0_1} and the partials one and two of f_{0_2} as well as one small frequency region with partial five of f_{0_1} at 375 Hz and partial four of f_{0_2} at 400 Hz, shown in figure 4.7.

From the previous test we know that our non-overlapped and non-interlaced tones share a constant magnitude level of -27 dB. Obviously the overlapped partials at 300 Hz increase their now joint energy by 6 dB to -21 dB. An increment in 6 dB reflects the doubling of the perceived loudness which in turn validates our test setup. The two tones are still present, increment the energy at their frequency area and do not mask each other at the same magnitude level, as if not being overlapped. Strictly speaking this statement is wrong or our test setup is erroneous because the three frequency regions with tangent sinusoids t_p and peaks p_k at the frequencies 86 Hz, 215 Hz and 387 Hz should as well increment their magnitude $|X(k)|$ due to the correlation of energy among them. But instead all peaks occur like in the non-tangent case at -27 dB and partial two of f_{0_1} exhibits an even lower magnitude $|X(k)|$. The validation of the correctness of the test setup is given by figure 4.8 where all three frequency

Figure 4.7: First example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 100 Hz with five partials each regions in question exhibit peaks p_k at magnitude levels of approximately -22 dB.

Figure 4.8: Second example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 100 Hz with five partials each

This behaviour can be explained again by AM beating. The peak at 300 Hz stays constant over frames at -21 dB and is not influenced by AM beating. This frame exemplifies a problem already indicated, all five partials for f_{01} and all but not partial five for f_{02} reside at a frequency area of either interlaced or overlapped sinusoids. Since no clean and non-influenced harmonic partials are available, influenced peak regions with a preferably symmetric main-lobe contour have to be employed and its

true magnitude $|X(k)|$ calculated. At this point we may think about a function examining how symmetric one spectral peak region is, starting at the DFT bin k with the maximum magnitude and comparing the descending left and right DFT bins until the first valley occurring at one side. Also, partial two of f_{0_1} can be treated by a nearest neighbour interpolation using the partials one and three of the same monophonic track $x_1(t)$. The new spectral representation for a source in such a situation can be incrementally interpolated for each harmonic partial h_p . Further investigation leads us to a situation illustrated by figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9: Third example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 100 Hz with five partials each

Here again all peaks being close or exactly at the frequency position for the partials h_p of f_{0_1} underly an interlaced or overlapped situation. Checking only for the symmetry of those spectral peak regions would in a wrong manner indicate that all peaks exhibit a symmetric main-lobe contour. But this does not reflect the obvious scrambling of the true main-lobe which should remain in a shape according to the Blackman-Harris window chosen. The partials one, three and five of f_{0_1} share a symmetric main-lobe contour but their width is too small while partial two of f_{0_1} has a too broad main-lobe when comparing these spectral peak regions against the 'healthy' main-lobe partial four of f_{0_1} . Therefore we extend the second assumption that we require an algorithm examining the similarity of spectral peaks p_k to the spectral shape of the main-lobe of the chosen window $w(t)$ in order retrieve the possibility to employ them as valid sinusoidal spectral peak region or that we have to correct the spectral shape of the spectral peak regions in question. Checking this similarity is fulfilled by the technical paradigms explained in chapter 3.3.4 for frequency-adaptive noise level estimation which examines the shape of spectral peaks regions in order to distinct between true sinusoidal components and spurious noisy peaks. This statement is even

more validated with the example given in figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10: Fourth example of two f_0 s at 75 Hz and 100 Hz with five partials each

4.4.2.2 Interlaced and overlapped partials with phases

Until now we followed only the first two criteria of how to identify influencing sinusoids in a polyphonic environment as proposed by Parson in 1976 and explained in chapter 3.3.7.1. Now we investigate the third criteria, the behaviour of the phases of spectral peak regions. For this we keep the previous example of two tangent and one overlapped frequency region of sinusoids and plot additionally the unwrapped phases of the spectra. We already know, for example from [Bonada, 2002] where stable and non-stable peaks are analysed in the context of transient processing, that ideally a stable sinusoid exhibits a flat phase spectrum over its continuation in terms of all DFT bins k comprised to describe the sinusoid. This is because the energy correlated with the DFT bins in question is introduced from one single frequency component of quasi-stationary property. This can as well occur when two or more sinusoids s_p overlap at exactly the same frequency position and with this describe the same situation, the frequency is stable and does not change for this spectral region. Therefore the phases do not have to describe a change in frequency for this phasor and remain constant over the spectral duration of the DFT bins for the sinusoidal component. A non-stable peak region or a region in the spectrum X not building out a peak contour in the magnitude spectrum $|X|$ exhibits a fluctuating or oblique contour of its phase spectrum Θ because the energy correlated with the weighting coefficient Ω_k for each DFT bin of index k is not a result of one or several sinusoidal components s_p of the exact same frequency ω . Therefore the phases θ_p have to describe a change in the

angle position $\angle\theta$ for each different phasor of different frequency ω on the unit circle.

Figure 4.11 illustrates the same frame measure than figure 4.7 but additionally depicts the phase spectrum Θ and uses the unit radians per second for the frequency scale and the phase values.

Figure 4.11: First magnitude spectrum $|X|$ and phase spectrum Θ example

As expected the non-influenced sinusoid, partial five of f_{02} , exhibits a constant phase spectrum for the duration of its appearance in the spectrum. Similarly but not perfectly constant behaves the phase spectrum corresponding to the overlap region of partial four of f_{01} and partial three of f_{02} . The three regions around the frequencies 86 Hz, 215 Hz and 387 Hz being described by tangent sinusoids t_p of 25 Hz frequency difference Δf each exhibit not a constant phase spectrum as does partial two of f_{01} at 150 Hz which shares a frequency difference Δf of 50 Hz with the neighbouring upper h_{p+1} and lower h_{p-1} harmonic partial.

Now we examine figure 4.12 which plots additionally the phase spectrum Θ of the third example which was shown by figure 4.9. Since we also have to treat the phases θ in tangent and overlapped regions, we have to investigate how to approach this problem. We could just use the phase spectrum Θ as additional indication of with which problem we deal, defined in our conclusions for the magnitude spectrum $|X|$ analysed above. Because the overlapped region exhibits already a constant phase spectrum we might keep the phase values. But we are not sure yet if we have to correct

Figure 4.12: Second magnitude spectrum $|X|$ and phase spectrum Θ example

its value, in accordance with the knowledge that we have to correct the magnitude values $|X(k)|$ for the overlapped sinusoids o_p . Furthermore we could discard the phase values θ of such regions and set for each spectral peak region the phases θ to a constant value reflecting the sinusoids frequency of the monophonic track $x_1(t)$ over the spectral duration of the sinusoid. Another approach could be to interpolate the phase spectrum Θ of tangent regions with the same function we will employ for the nearest neighbour interpolation and reflect with this the right value as well as the right phase contour for the spectral region in question. But it may be that we have to find different solutions when dealing with a higher amount of polyphony. Until now we just analysed two synthetically generated harmonic streams with five partials only and have already to deal with the fact that all partials but one are influenced by the other source, as again illustrated by figure 4.13.

As last step in the analysis of interlaced and overlapped sinusoids we investigate further the behaviour for a polyphony of three sources. In order to employ a more realistic setup we inspect the three MIDI notes C2 with partials at 64.41 Hz, 130.81 Hz, 196.22 Hz, 261.62 Hz and 327.03 Hz, G2 with partials at 98 Hz, 196 Hz, 294 Hz, 392 Hz and 490 Hz as well as E3 with partials at 164.81 Hz, 329.62 Hz, 494.43 Hz, 659.24 Hz and 824.05 Hz. With this we have to deal with three mostly overlapping situations at 192 Hz with 0.22 Hz difference, at 328 Hz with 2.59 Hz difference and at 492 Hz with 4.43 Hz difference in frequency. We want to know if new behaviours will be introduced when the polyphony increases and conclude possible solutions, depicted

Figure 4.13: Third magnitude spectrum $|X|$ and phase spectrum Θ example

by figure 4.14.

We realize from the frequency region between 60 Hz - 240 Hz that the occurrence of several sinusoidal components s_p being close enough in frequency together can lead to one single combined smooth spectral peak region. Only one peak is detected for this frequency region with one peak p_1 at 187.9 Hz where the peaks p_k are distinct with frequency differences Δf of 31 Hz - 35 Hz and two peaks occur at the same narrow-band at 196 Hz. We note that the phases θ behave according to the spectral peak contour and seem not to need any extra handling. We come to our **sixth assumption** that we treat the phases θ in the same manner like the magnitude spectrum $|X|$ and employ the same algorithmic paradigm chosen for $|X|$ at the phase spectrum Θ . This surely excludes the magnitude correction from assumption three. We propose another type of spectral peaks p_k for polyphonic environments where more than two sinusoids s_p from different sources occur within the same frequency region, as an extension to the first assumption. We call them irresolvable peaks i_p , according to [Every, 2006]. This type of peak requires the insertion of a sinusoidal harmonic model because a peak interpolation from non-overlapped neighbours, as was one approach in [Every, 2006], is not anymore applicable.

Figure 4.14: Fourth magnitude spectrum $|X|$ and phase spectrum Θ example

4.4.3 AM/FM beating analysis

In this chapter we want to examine more profound the different assumption we stated in the previous chapter and investigate with this different scenarios of AM/FM beating for our fixed STFT parameter setup of FFT size $N=4096$, window size $M=2061$ and $\text{hop}=412$. We want to check if there is a certain threshold in frequency difference under below which the overlapped situation of sinusoids s_p is valid. We refer to an overlapped situation when only one peak p_k occurs within a frequency region where two or more sinusoids reside with a small difference in frequency Δf and the spectral peak region resembles the 'sharp' main-lobe shape of the window W . This can be seen contrary to assumption two which poses the existence of non-symmetric spectral peak regions. Furthermore we examine if there exists as well a certain threshold in frequency difference under which an interlaced partial situation occur, which refers to the existence of two non-symmetric peaks with a main-lobe not resembling the shape of the window type. As well we want to evaluate if such a possibly existing frequency difference threshold is frequency dependent or absolute.

For this we employ two tones and inspect their spectral behaviour over frames. Per test we gradually let them drift away in frequency from each other. With this we investigate AM beating, as indicated in chapter 3.3.7.2, and FM beating, as indicated in chapter 4.4.2. Additionally we set different amplitudes a_p for both sinusoids s_1 and s_2 in order to retrieve the mutual influence depending on the energy of both

sinusoidal components.

4.4.3.1 Test with 2 Hz frequency difference

Due to the centering of our zero-phase windowed frames around time instant zero we require three frames at the beginning of processing until the signal is fully 'swung in'. We start therefore the analysis always at frame four. For two tones, as shown in figure 4.15, with fundamental frequencies f_{0_1} at 99 Hz and f_{0_2} at 101 Hz and an amplitude a_p of 0.9 in time domain for both tones we receive a perfect symmetric main-lobe according to the employed window. We observe a peak p_k at -7.08 dB and a constant phase spectrum Θ across the main-lobe of the sinusoid s_p . One frame further in time the magnitudes $|X|$ decreased not visibly by less than 1 dB while the unwrapped phase spectrum $\Delta_P\Theta$ remains constant but changed its value significantly. While stepping further through the frames the magnitude values $|X|$ decrease more. The amount of decrease increases with each step which can be observed by the difference between frame 26 and frame 27 which is significantly higher than the difference between the frames four and five. As well the phase spectrum Θ exhibits a more and more oblique instead of horizontal contour for all DFT bins k describing the sinusoidal peak regions which we observed with an initial frequency difference of 0 Hz. Until now we experience AM beating with a decrease in magnitude $|X|$ from frame four until frame 27. At frame 28 we observe the first spectral frame for this test where FM beating occurs. Our peak interpolation algorithm retrieves two peaks, one at the left frequency side at 76.03 Hz and - 38.35 dB as well as another one at the right frequency side at 123.77 Hz and - 38.33 dB. We note to experience for this test a magnitude difference due to amplitude modulation of approximately $|X_{maxdiff}| = ||X(p_{k=max})| - |X(p_{k=min})|| = ||-7.08dB| - |-38.35dB|| = 31.27$ dB as a result of no difference in amplitude from both sinusoidal amplitudes $a_1 = a_2 = 0.9$.

In order to understand this behaviour better it is wise to look at the time domain signal produced for this setup, which we depict in figure 4.16. We see clearly the well-known amplitude modulation as the heterodyning envelope which turns to nearly 0 amplitude at the time instants 0.25 s and 0.75 s. Since our frequency difference of two Hz denotes a time period of $T_1 = 1 / 2 \text{ Hz} = 0.5$ s it is easy to show that at time instant 0.25 s we measure frame number 28 because 0.25 seconds at a sampling rate f_s of 44100 are represented by 11025 samples which we advance with a hop size of 412 in 26 frames plus two frames extra due to the centering around time instant zero at the beginning. At this point we experience the single FM beating which as well appears at frame 81 corresponding to time instant 0.75 seconds.

Clearly the different amounts of magnitude changes in dB described earlier in this chapter follow the amplitude envelope we observe in the time domain according to the beating frequency $f_{beat} = |f_2 - f_1| / 2$, known from amplitude modulation. The time intervals between occurring FM beating time instants are determined according

(a) Frame 4

(b) Frame 5

(c) Frame 26

(d) Frame 27

(e) Frame 28

(f) Frame 29

Figure 4.15: AM and FM beating analysis for two tones of 99 Hz and 101 Hz

Figure 4.16: Time domain signal for two sinusoids at 99 Hz and 101 Hz

to the difference in frequency of the two sinusoids h_1 and h_2 , expressed by the beating frequency f_{beat} .

4.4.3.2 Test with 20 Hz frequency difference

To further investigate this behaviour for a later overlapping partial treatment we create another test setup with two fundamental frequencies at 90 Hz and 110 Hz, which we depict in figure 4.17. We measure at frame four for the left frequency side a peak at $p_1 = 76.92$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -18.53$ dB and to the right a peak at $p_2 = 123.02$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(k)| = -18.56$ dB. We note that a change in the frequency difference to $\Delta f = 20$ Hz resulted in a magnitude change of AM beating but not a change in frequency due to FM beating. Two frames further we measure the temporary maximum magnitude at one single peak $p_1 = 100.01$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -7.84$ dB. At frame nine we evaluate a clear FM beating with two distinct peaks at $p_1 = 73.6$ Hz and $p_2 = 126.13$ Hz at magnitudes of $|X(p_1)| = -19.25$ dB and $|X(p_2)| = -19.32$ dB due to a very distinct phase modulation with a constant horizontal phase continuation at different levels corresponding to the instantaneous frequencies encoded in the phase representation. This pattern of FM beating with two distinct peaks due to two distinct phase levels at low magnitude levels and AM beating with changing magnitudes over frames due to amplitude modulation is repeating, as we illustrate with the measures depicted for the frames 12, 14 and 17.

(a) Frame 4

(b) Frame 6

(c) Frame 9

(d) Frame 12

(e) Frame 14

(f) Frame 17

Figure 4.17: AM and FM beating analysis for two tones of 90 Hz and 110 Hz

4.4.3.3 Test with 20 Hz frequency and 5 dB amplitude difference

Finally we test the more applicable and required scenario for the same sinusoidal frequencies of $f_1 = 90$ Hz and $f_2 = 110$ Hz but with different amplitudes $a_1 = 0.9$ and $a_2 = 0.5$. We illustrate the results in figure 4.18. With the plot from frame four we immediately think about the second assumption from the previous sub-chapter which claims the requirement of an identification and correction of wrong main-lobe shapes. We expect two peaks within the frequency band of question but encounter only one peak p_1 with a non-symmetric main-lobe. A second peak being only partially visible is not found by the interpolation function because the frequency region in question does not fulfill the criteria for a peak and we measure only one peak at $p_1 = 82.2$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -16.14$ dB. We have to deal with how to properly assign the measured energy to both sinusoidal components. Since we only know the score but not the amplitudes in the final application we pose another **seventh assumption** that we have to calculate the true magnitude of the sinusoidal components suffering from AM beating in order to be able to correct the magnitude for each partial according to the third assumption and distribute the instantaneously measured energy to all harmonic partial in the frequency region accordingly. This new assumption will not be added to the phase treatment of assumption six.

From chapter 3.3.7.2 and from a re-check at Klapuris work in [Klapuri, 2004] we know how to calculate the magnitudes for two sinusoids experiencing amplitude modulated beating. Before any calculation we measured the magnitudes in the spectrum for both sinusoids in a clean monophonic environment. The amplitude $a_1 = 0.9$ of sinusoid s_1 in the time domain corresponds to a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -6.93$ dB in the spectral domain while sinusoid s_1 with an amplitude of $a_1 = 0.5$ for sinusoid s_2 leads to a magnitude of $|X(p_2)| = -12.04$ dB.

The beating amplitude is defined by the sinusoid with the smaller magnitude. We find the highest magnitudes at the frames plotted to the right. At frame six the algorithm retrieves a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -9.9334$ dB, at frame 12 we measure $|X(p_1)| = -9.8892$ and at frame 17 the magnitude is $|X(p_1)| = -9.7742$, leading to a maximum magnitude for this small example of $|X_{max}| = -9.7742$ dB. Frame 14 behaves similar to frame four because the interpolation algorithm retrieves a peak at $p_1 = 82.62$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -16.03$ dB. Frame nine instead poses the same problem according to assumption seven but gives us access to the magnitude of the second peak. We measure at the left side a peak at $p_1 = 81$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -16.48$ dB and to the right a peak at $p_2 = 135.76$ Hz with a magnitude of $|X(k)| = -28.77$ dB. Thus we measure the lowest magnitude of $|X(p_1)| = -16.48$ dB at frame nine. The estimated beating magnitude is therefore $|X_{est-min}| = |X_{max}| - |X_{min}| = 9.7742$ dB - 16.48 dB = -6.71 dB. We introduce an error of $|X_{error}| = |X(p_1)| - |X_{est-min}| = 0.22$ dB which is determined by the negligible failure of interpolation and by not measuring at the exact points in time where FM beating occurs due to the change in phase and the points of lowest amplitude of the

(a) Frame 4

(b) Frame 6

(c) Frame 9

(d) Frame 12

(e) Frame 14

(f) Frame 17

Figure 4.18: AM and FM beating analysis for two tones of 90 Hz and 110 Hz with different magnitudes

heterodyning amplitude modulation envelope.

Figure 4.19: Time domain signal for two sinusoids at 90 Hz and 110 Hz

Again we plot the time domain signal for better understanding, shown in figure 4.19. We retrieve visually the heterodyning envelope of amplitude modulation with a time period of $T_{beat} = 0.05$ s which corresponds to the beating frequency $f_{beat} = 1/T_{beat} = 1 / 0.05$ s = 20 Hz. We note the lower modulation in amplitude a_{mod} due to the bigger difference in frequency Δf .

We plot the time domain signal for this setup with different amplitudes for comparison with the previous example, shown in figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: Time domain signal for two sinusoids at 90 Hz and 110 Hz with different amplitudes

Since the beating envelope and its magnitude is determined by the sinusoid with the lower amplitude we approximate with the measures the magnitude -6.93 dB of sinusoid s_1 by the difference of $|X_{max}|$ and $|X_{min}| = -6.71$ dB. Because of the known score we are aware of the frequency difference Δf which determines the beating rate.

With this we additionally know the frames with lowest magnitudes and when FM beating occurs. At those time instants we are able to compute the magnitude of the second sinusoid s_2 because two peaks occur within this frame with a magnitude difference according to s_2 . This is independent of the current amplitude modulation depth. We calculate $|X(s_2)| = |X_{p_1}| - |X_{p_2}| = -16.48 \text{ dB} - -28.77 \text{ dB} = 12.29 \text{ dB}$. The error introduced is $|X_{error}| = ||X(p_2)| - |X(s_2)|| = -12.04 \text{ dB} - -12.29 \text{ dB} = 0.25 \text{ dB}$. Test at further FM beating frames produced less error in dB.

4.4.4 Overlapping partials analysis summary

We summarize our assumptions for a better overview of the situations identified and how we want to treat them.

1. Checking for two or more peaks p_k in a narrow-band Δf does not necessarily identify overlapping partials o_p . We utilize information from the score *a priori* to expect narrow-band frequency regions of four types:
 - Only one sinusoid occurs, exhibiting one 'healthy' peak region.
 - Several overlapped sinusoids $o_{p_1} \dots o_{p_k}$ exhibit one joint 'healthy' peak region.
 - Several interlaced sinusoids $t_{p_1} \dots t_{p_k}$ exhibit several peaks in their frequency region.
 - Several sinusoids are interlaced t_p or overlapped o_p , are irresolvable and exhibit a continuous smooth spectral region.
2. Identify situations where a sinusoidal component is only partially or completely not visible and does not fulfill the criteria of a peak by checking for the true spectral shape of spectral peaks according to the employed window. Correct the main-lobe contour to the true main-lobe shape.
3. AM beating: Correct the magnitude of irresolvable, interlaced and overlapped peaks by measuring the AM beating envelope depth of sinusoids.
4. FM beating: Correct the magnitude of irresolvable, interlaced and overlapped peaks by measuring the magnitude difference at FM beating time instants for sinusoids of lower amplitude.
5. Investigate besides AM beating how to retrieve the true magnitude belonging to the corresponding sources for each measured peak region in order to distribute the instantaneously measured energy to all harmonic partial in the frequency region.

6. Implement an algorithm for nearest neighbour interpolation to correct peaks exhibiting not the shape of the window main-lobe.
7. Implement an harmonic partial insertion algorithm were nearest neighbour interpolation is not feasible.
8. Treat the phases θ in the same manner like the magnitude spectrum $|X|$ and employ the same algorithmic paradigm chosen for $|X|$ at the phase spectrum Θ , excluding transient modelling, magnitude correction and energy distribution.

We analysed properly different scenarios of tangent and overlapped sinusoids per frame. What we didn't take into account is the requirement of a smooth continuation of magnitude $|X|$, phase and frequency for each harmonic partials trajectory. Even a perfect treatment of mutually influencing partials from a frame-only view will lead to artefacts when a jump in magnitude $|X|$, phase θ or frequency ω over frames is introduced.

4.5 Harmonic estimation

4.5.1 Spectral peak region classification

In order to treat each sinusoidal component of the signal measured per frame as spectral peak region in the spectrum we require the examination of its spectral shape, as explained in the previous chapter 4.4.

We execute the interpolation function in order to retrieve the peaks we measure within each spectral frame. First we analyse for each peak its corresponding spectral region until the first valley found to the lower and upper frequency side. Then we correlate the spectral peak region with the spectral representation of the employed 92 dB Blackman-Harris window. In order to be able to employ different correlation algorithms we need to adjust the size of each spectral region to the main-lobe width of the windows.

We could interpolate a too long spectral region or extrapolate a too short spectral region but would introduce with this an error by not reflecting to the evaluating correlation function the true behaviour of the spectral peak region. Therefore we use a linear ramp interpolation on the edges of the non-fitting spectral regions, starting with the magnitude of the last valid DFT bin. This introduces the required error and reflects that the spectral shape of the spectral region does not match the windows main-lobe shape, as depicted in figure 4.21.

For this we evaluated at an initial implementation step the Pearson product-moment correlation, as well as distance measures on different heuristic peak region consideration paradigms.

Figure 4.21: Illustration of the linear ramp interpolation for spectral peak regions

1. Pearson correlation
2. Direct summation of differences
3. Euclidean distance
4. Squared Euclidean distance
5. Peak region length
6. Symmetry of half-lobes

We summarize the observed performance for each tested spectral peak classification approach.

Pearson correlation:

The Pearson's correlation coefficient can be conveniently computed with the Matlab function `corr(x)`, along with the p-value for further statistical analysis. In general the Pearson correlation gives a good approximation due to its intrinsic nature of correlating the contour and energy of signals. In detail it suffers for this task from its zero-mean and unit-variance approach by subtracting the mean from each sample and dividing each result by the overall deviation of the distribution. This might be in general a good accomplishment but when the spectral shape of the peak region is for example influenced by several sinusoidal components, exhibits a too broad contour but

still follows the general overall shape of the window main-lobe the Pearson correlation still correlates too good with a peak region which we want to identify as non-valid. Especially the desired error introduced with the linear ramp on the edges of too short peak region results in a high and not low correlation with the window main-lobe shape. Also the additional p-value of the employed Matlab function did not overcome this behaviour. Hence we cannot rely on the Pearson correlation paradigm for this task.

Direct difference summation:

The fast implementation of this easy algorithm delivers surprisingly good results by evaluating the sample-wise distance between the measured peak region and the window shape. Its only weak point is the recurring type I error by rejecting the null hypothesis of the first partial in the spectrum belonging to the fundamental frequency. This false positive error occurs because the first harmonic does not share a neighbouring partial to the lower left in frequency, drifts from the ideal window shape away towards the DC component of the Fourier transform and fools with this an actually right result.

Euclidean distance:

The well-known Euclidean distance measure as explained in chapter 2.3 achieves the overall best results in discriminating the shape of spectral peaks regions and is employed further.

Squared Euclidean distance:

The simple square-root of the Euclidean distance measure achieves the same overall good results as the standard Euclidean distance and is not further employed due to its similarity to the employed standard Euclidean distance.

Peak region length:

A simple but effective way to avoid the selection of peak regions influenced from different sources or the selection of spurious peaks from window side-lobes, modulated noise components etc. is the examination of the peak region lengths in DFT bins. Setting a threshold to exclude too small peak regions is employed throughout this research work.

Symmetry of half-lobes:

The Harmonic Estimation part of the implemented software system retrieves for each peak region the spectral position of the DFT bin exhibiting a local maximum as well as the DFT bins with a local minimum to the left and right frequency region. Examining the plain difference between the left and right length corresponding to the half-lobes of a windowed sinusoid in the spectral representation achieves in theory

good results. Influenced and overlapped partials can be identified in an easy manner by evaluating the symmetry of half-lobe lengths. Practical tests showed even for a monophonic environment that not allowing bigger half-lobe differences results in a worse audio quality. Despite this observation the symmetry of half-lobes according to their difference in length is further employed as peak classification measure.

With this the indicated methods to retrieve a frequency-adaptive noise level estimation from chapter 3.3.4 are not implemented due to the short time available to do so and due to the sufficient performance of the mentioned rough heuristic approaches employing simple distance measures. The not yet indicated but more suitable work in [Zivanovic et al., 2008] utilizes an adaptive threshold determination to classify spectral peaks but is skipped as well due to limitations in time.

4.5.2 AM beating analysis

In order to exploit AM beating and the with along coming FM beating due to phase modulation dependent on the frequency difference of overlapping partials we implement a birth and death algorithm to track overlapping harmonic partials over frames. We employ the same f_0 -dependent frequency range as explained in chapter 4.6 to detect more than one harmonic partial frequency within a narrow-band. We rely on the f_0 information from the score. If more than one partial frequency occurs within the frequency range we start to track this partial over the following frames (birth). If in the next frame the same frequency occurs we continue tracking. Else we delete the tracking of this frequency partial (death). Before deleting the track we check if the tracking occurred over a minimal frame-treshold of two.

From the time instant of birth until death we assign the closest interpolated peak within the frequency range according to the Bark scale approach from chapter 4.6 to the partial track. We don't assign its frequency but store its magnitude to the partial track and check at each frame if this partial exhibits a higher magnitude in order to retrieve the highest magnitude according to the AM beating envelope. Simultaneously we track as well for the minimum magnitude of the closest interpolated partial. If we measure at one frame a minimum magnitude we update our partial track in order to retrieve the minimum of the AM beating envelope at FM beating time instant. At each update of the minimum magnitude we search for the closest partial around the current one and store its magnitude as well. With this we measure the magnitude difference at FM beating time instant in order to resolve the magnitude of the second sinusoid causing AM/FM beating.

4.6 Harmonic processing

This chapter explains algorithmic parts of the implemented system for harmonic audio object processing.

We cannot know how many partials one source carries along with its signal representation above a magnitude threshold. Therefore we interpolate all found peaks and run over their length in a loop while trying to assign simultaneously harmonic frequencies according to the current f_0 to the monophonic tracks representation. We want to avoid as much as possible the assignment of peaks from other tracks to the current one.

With this we try to avoid another possible approach which would interpolate and represent all found peaks in the spectrum to one single track, including 'wrong' peaks from other monophonic tracks. Especially the pitch-transposition algorithm would introduce errors by employing with the Harmonic Assignment paradigm peaks from other streams in our polyphonic environment. A narrow-band frequency region can be identified to contain overlapping partials as mentioned in chapter 3.3.7.1 by detecting several peaks in the corresponding frequency region, by a non-symmetric peak contour and the behaviour in the corresponding phase region.

We examine a certain frequency range for each harmonic partial in order to assure that only one peak occurs for the non-overlapping partial case. We define the bandwidth of a narrow-band heuristically by setting a frequency range per frame of half the minimum of the lowest fundamental frequency for the whole spectrum. We set a variable if more than one harmonic partial occurs within the f_0 -dependent range.

The assignment of one valid peak region according to the spectral peak classification utilizes a perceptually motivated frequency-dependent bandwidth as a function of the Bark scale. We check for each harmonic frequency its membership to which Bark band, add one % of the corresponding Bark bands center frequency plus a fixed frequency difference of 20 Hz. The Bark scale is defined until the frequency edge 15.5 kHz with a highest center frequency of 13.5 kHz. In [Pohlmann, 2000] one additional centre frequency of 18775 Hz is provided. This enables us to employ reasonable narrow-band frequency ranges up to the Nyquist limit for a common sampling rate of 44.1 kHz.

4.6.1 Transient modelling

The automatic detection of note onsets is not required due to the available timing input from the pre-annotated score. The duration of the transient oscillation at the beginning of each note is different for different instrument types and partially for different modes of expression. The time instants of all transient onsets but not the transient offsets are known. Because of this reason and the requirement for the distinction between transient and pure sinusoidal components in a polyphonic audio

stream for a Phase Vocoder based transformation process the modelling of transient peak regions is necessary. The latter requirement avoids transient smearing resulting from time-scaling and pitch-transposition.

We implement equation 3.3 from chapter 3.3.3 but avoid the re-positioning of the windowed frame to the new location at the synthesis stage as well as an evaluation of the COG threshold dependent on the chosen window. Hence we roughly examine the peak-wise behaviour of the COG at frames containing transient events according to the information from the score and set an heuristic threshold following the influencing behaviour of the negative phase derivate $-\frac{\partial\phi(\omega,t_m)}{\partial\omega}$.

4.6.2 Nearest neighbour interpolation

The selection of neighbouring peaks with the exclusive criterium of being the nearest non-overlapped peak does not produce perceptually well perceived output streams due to not taken into consideration the spectral shape of the peak. Therefore additional criteria for the selection of one neighbouring peak region have to be taken into consideration. The interpolation should ideally select two peaks underlying the most closest spectral magnitude, a spectral shape and length according to the windows main-lobe and thus having the same amount of DFT bins to their left and right of the DFT bin exhibiting a local maximum. In practice this selection is not easy to achieve.

Checking for a spectral peak region not being influenced by a nearby sinusoid from another track by employing knowledge from the MIDI score is a bad choice either. The algorithm has to search a too far distance until a really pure non-influenced and non-overlapping frequency region is encountered. In most scenarios very less pure harmonic spectral regions occur per frame which worsens this approach.

The interpolated spectral region as output can only be as long as the smaller part of both region sides. The nearest neighbour peak selection algorithm shall retrieve peak regions with ideally the same half-lobe size in DFT bins. The linear interpolation introduces an approximation in magnitude to the interpolated spectral region between the magnitudes of both neighbouring regions employed. This approximation has to be corrected according to the spectral envelope contour of the frequency region. The example in figure 4.22 illustrates a nearest neighbour interpolation before the applied energy correction.

We summarize approaches implemented for the nearest neighbour interpolation.

- Search for peaks resembling the windows main-lobe shape instead of searching for pure non-influenced spectral regions.
- Set a frequency threshold to avoid the selection of too far peak regions.
- Minimize half-lobe distances.

Figure 4.22: Nearest neighbour interpolation for overlapped peak regions

- Correct the interpolated magnitude.

With this the paradigm called nearest neighbour interpolation changes and does not address anymore the consideration of non-overlapped peak regions but applies the interpolation of spectral peaks from overlapped regions exhibiting a 'healthy' spectral shape.

4.6.3 Spectral peak region generation

The nearest neighbour interpolation is not applicable at the borders of the Fourier transform. Especially the perceptually important region at the beginning of the positive frequency representation comprising the first harmonic partials with the highest energy does not allow the interpolation from peaks of lower frequency which do not exist. For this scenario the generation of spectral peak regions and their insertion at the harmonic partial locations in frequency is required

We transform the window generated in the time domain to a clean spectrum, search for its maximum peak as well as the left and right local minimum before the first side-lobe occurs and employ this as ideal shape of a windowed sinusoid in the spectral representation.

The current status of the implemented algorithm is to include a window main-lobe of minimum length given as threshold to the system, along with a constant horizontal phase contour at zero radians. Further programming could identify regions in the spectrum where additional harmonic partials belonging to the current fundamental

frequency of the current source are left out and are not inserted due to less space available in the corresponding frequency narrow-band.

4.6.4 Plain magnitude correction

From the assumptions retrieved in the previous chapter we implement a simple approach to reduce the magnitude of overlapped peak regions by -6 dB with the expectation that this won't produce a perfect output audio quality but might improve the performance slightly.

4.6.5 AM/FM beat exploitation for magnitude correction

From the AM beating analysis algorithm, explained in chapter 4.5.2, we now the magnitudes of the two sinusoids causing AM/FM beating. The AM/FM beating correction algorithm resides at the end of the harmonic processing function and corrects for spectral peak regions being tagged as overlapped the magnitudes accordingly. We enable either the exploitation of AM or FM beating to correct one spectral region for the time being. The current implementation suffers severely from not knowing which magnitude has to be employed to correct which of the two occurring sinusoids and introduces artefacts. It is believed that a better awareness of the occurring harmonic partials and their instantaneous frequencies would overcome the current drawback of the implement system. For example a partial tracking algorithm based on linear prediction as indicated in the chapter for future work and proposed in [Lagrange et al., 2003] would improve the AM/FM beating exploitation approach.

4.7 Pitch-transposition

At the beginning of each frame within each transformation function applied to each estimated monophonic track we update the time instant for the analysis t_a^u according to its corresponding input pointer. We represent the time scale in seconds and divide therefore by the sampling rate f_s . We update the pulse onset times for the input t_n^i and pitch-transpositioned output t_n^o in dependence to its corresponding pitch periods, according to equation 3.36 and 3.37.

We search for each new pitch-transpositioned harmonic partial within a frame description retrieved from the harmonic estimation and processing functions for the closest valid spectral peak region description. The required shift in DFT bins from this peak region to our ideal harmonic frequency position is calculated. Since this frequency position lies in almost all cases on a non-integer sub-bin position we interpolate the input spectral peak region to the ideal frequency position and have to introduce a rounding error, which is for the worst case 0.5 bins.

Applying a pure harmonic frequency distribution to the chosen Phase Vocoder model by setting the pulse onset times for the pitch periods of the input and output signal introduces an inharmonic frequency relation between the partials taken from the input signal and the pure harmonic model, shown in the following Matlab code.

```

1 % pure harmonic model for each partial i
2 fharm = i*f0*N/Fs;
3 % input+output center frequency for the harmonic sinusoidal
4 Wkin = 2*pi*fharm*Fs/N;
5 Wkout = 2*pi*fharm*fscale*Fs/N;

```

This may introduce phasiness due to the loss of the vertical phase coherence. Therefore the real interpolated frequency of each sinusoid accounts for the intrinsic inharmonic nature of music instruments producing harmonic sinusoidal partials residing not at an exact integer multiple of the fundamental frequency, while possessing a harmonic relation between the partials. The measured and interpolated input frequency $iploc(k)$ for partial k accounts for the real pitch-transposition factor between each partial and its new pure harmonic frequency position. This accomplishes a pitch-transpositioned output signal without an inharmonic frequency distribution and phasiness.

```

1 % pure harmonic model for each partial i
2 fharm = i*f0*N/Fs;
3 % input+output center frequency for the harmonic sinusoidal
4 Wkin = 2*pi*iploc(k)*Fs/N;
5 Wkout = 2*pi*fharm*fscale*Fs/N;

```

4.8 Time-scaling

The extension of this Phase Vocoder approach from pitch-transposition to time-scaling is straightforward. As explained in [Bonada, 2000] we just have to look at each synthesis frame time instant to the right in positive time at the analysis time scale. There we check if we have to insert or drop one frame according to our synthesis frame continuation. We keep both frame rates for the analysis and synthesis time scale constant, counted in frames. In order to achieve a compression or stretching in time according to the desired time-scaling factor we introduce a 'faking' time scale between both input and output. For this we set up a hop-size 'fakeout' for the synthesis part being inverse proportional to the time-scaling factor and address with this each synthesis output frame 'foutFrame'.

```

1 % initialize the 'faking' time scale
2 fout = 0;
3 fakeout = round(hop/tscale);
4 foutFrame = round(fout/hop)+1;
5 % input pointer update at loop-start
6 if inFrame < foutFrame && tscale > 1.0
7     pin = pin + hop;
8     inFrame = round(pin/hop);
9 end
10 while inFrame < foutFrame && tscale < 1.0
11     pin = pin + hop;
12     inFrame = round(pin/hop);
13 end
14 if tscale == 1.0
15     pin = pin + hop;
16 end
17 % ...
18 % apply pitch-transposition
19 % ...
20 fout = fout + fakeout;
21 foutFrame = round(fout/hop);
22 inFrame = round(pin/hop);

```

For a slower playback speed with time-scaling factors bigger than one we only update the input pointer `pin` and its corresponding frame counter `inFrame` if it remains below its counterpart `foutFrame`. With this we may insert one input frame twice or more times while constantly advancing the output pointer `fout` by a bigger hop-size `fakeout`. Time-compression for faster playback speed with time-scaling factors smaller than one drops frames according to the position of the input and output frame counter `inFrame` and `foutFrame`. The input pointer `pin` is updated until the amount of the constantly advanced output counter `foutFrame` is reached, which may leave out input frames.

Dropping or inserting frames requires naturally to adjust the phases of the processed peak regions due to the stretching or compression of its signal continuation in time in order to maintain the horizontal phase coherence between the sinusoidal phasors. The phasors may loose with this their smooth continuation over frames. Thus we have to introduce to the Phase Vocoder model the new output time scale in order to update the phasors retaining a smooth phase continuation, which is called horizontal phase coherence.

To do so we exchange the time-scale t_a^u accounting for the input time instant at the synthesis side by the new output time-scale t_s^u in order to account for the time-scaled output axis and its output time instants. Naturally we advance t_s^u per frame with a constant hop size. Now the pitch-transpositioned output t_n^o , as explained in the previous chapter, accounts as well for the output pulse onset time instant for both pitch-transpositioned and time-scaled sinusoidal phasors. With this the update of t_n^o

for each output pitch period stays as defined by equation 3.37 but is updated according to the new output time-scale t_s^u . This changes equation 3.37 from chapter 3.6.3 to equation 4.4.

$$\phi^o(t_s^u) = \phi^o(t_n^o) + \omega_o(t_s^u - t_n^o) \quad (4.4)$$

Now we have to ensure that the phase of the output spectra ϕ^o resides at the new output pulse onset time instant t_n^o according to t_s^u . Naturally we keep the closest input onset time instant t_n^i to measure the phase $\phi^i(t_n^i)$ from the input signal in order to retain its relation to the input frequency ω_i . But the output pulse onset time instant t_n^o has now to be closest to its corresponding output frequency ω_o to retain their relation as well. Therefore we update as well equation 3.40 from chapter 3.6.3 to equation 4.5.

$$\phi^o(t_s^u) = \phi^i(t_n^i) + \omega_o(t_s^u - t_n^o) - \omega_i(t_n^i - t_n^o) \quad (4.5)$$

Now we add to the measured input phase $\phi^i(t_n^i)$ the instantaneous output frequency ω_o at frame t_s^u and subtract the instantaneous input frequency ω_i from the analysis frame t_a^u . With this the rotation of the phasors on the unit circle for combined pitch-transposition and time-scaling is expressed by the complex number z in equation.

$$z = e^{j\omega_o(t_s^u - t_n^o) - j\omega_i(t_a^u - t_n^i)} \quad (4.6)$$

Figure 4.23 illustrates a combined time-scaling and pitch-transposition implementation.

Figure 4.23: Combined time-scaling and pitch-transposition

The example employs a factor of 2.0 to decrease the playback speed and a factor of 2.57 to decrease the fundamental frequency f_0 . Note that the length of a synthesis frame equals the length of an analysis frame, despite the picture might lead to a different observation. A time-scaling factor of 2 leads to the insertion of two synthesis frames per one analysis frame. Simultaneously the rate of the pulse onset times t_n^i is reduced at the output stage, leading to a lower fundamental frequency f_0 or longer pitch periods $T = 1/f_0$ between each pulse onset time instant t_n^o for synthesis.

Chapter 5

Test methodology

Without music, life would be a mistake - Friedrich Nietzsche

5.1 Hypotheses

The noted assumptions from chapter 4.4.4 are combined into several hypotheses claimed in this chapter. Each hypothesis addresses one or several algorithms implemented in the software system. We test the algorithms and its corresponding claimed hypothesis by creating several test scenarios accordingly. We measure the performance of the algorithms for each test with objective evaluation algorithms as explained in 2.3 and conduct a listening test for the same test scenarios. The analysis of the results as explained in chapter 2.4 with MANOVA and a Tukey test in order to evaluate and validate the hypotheses by possibly rejecting their null hypothesis are exchanged by a one-way ANOVA. As well a planned final regression test, as for example executed in [Minard et al., 2008], in order to relate our observations from the objective and subjective evaluation methodologies to avoid misleading conclusions is left out due to time limitations.

5.1.1 First hypothesis

We combine the first two assumptions from chapter 4.4.4 about the appearance, detection and possibly correction of different spectral peak region types. We claim that information from the MIDI score to identify overlapped frequency regions is required for their detection but this knowledge is not essential. More important is the distinction between valid spectral peak regions following the main-lobe contour of the window, exhibiting a minimum length, and containing mostly symmetric half-lobe lengths. We claim the importance to correct spectral peak regions being tagged

as non-valid by the spectral peak classification system, as explained in chapter 4.5.1. We validate or reject this first hypothesis with test one in chapter 5.4.1.

5.1.2 Second hypothesis

The second hypothesis claims the requirement of an magnitude correction paradigm to distribute the energy in overlapped regions to each participating harmonic partial of the corresponding single sources. We include the assumptions three, four and five from overlapped analysis summary. We implement an algorithm to exploit AM and FM beating in order to measure the true magnitude values of two overlapped or tangent sinusoids in one frequency narrow-band and to correct the magnitude measured at the current frame for the addressed sinusoidal components. We correct the magnitude to the value measured a) by the maximum magnitude of the spectral region in question and b) the magnitude of the DFT bin where the maximum of the interpolated or generated spectral peak region to be inserted resides. We address this hypothesis as well with the approach from 4.6.4 by subtracting 6 dB. We validate or reject this second hypothesis with test two in chapter 5.4.2.

5.1.3 Third hypothesis

The importance of a nearest neighbour interpolation or harmonic generation algorithm to correct spectral peak regions tagged as non-valid due to a wrong spectral shape is claimed by the third hypothesis. We validate or reject this third hypothesis with test three in chapter 5.4.3.

5.2 Objective evaluation

The objective measure algorithms compute for each frame the perceptually related spectral evaluation paradigms Mel-Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCC), Linear Predictive Coding (LPC) and Line Spectrum Frequencies (LSF). We employ an order of 12 for LPC and LSF and examine the first 12 MFCC coefficients. Per frame we receive for each feature vector one value from the Pearson correlation, from the direct summation of their absolute difference and from the sum of the Euclidean distance. We normalize the latter two distance measures by the length of the feature vector per frame and by the amount of frames for the overall result. Additionally we execute the Pearson correlation and both distance measures directly on the waveform output stream to be compared. Note that the summation of differences and the summation of Euclidean distances exhibits higher values for less similarity while the Pearson correlation results in higher values due to congruent energies for higher similarities. The Pearson correlation is defined in the range of $[-1, 1]$. This range is kept for the

correlation of the waveform samples but is lost for MFCC, LPC and LSF due to the frame-wise approach.

5.3 Subjective evaluation

In contrary to the desired test methodology indicated in chapter 2.4, the tests for this work are reduced to compare one single setup in terms of polyphony and instrument type against different algorithmic setups. This decision is taken because of the low overall quality achieved as final output which neglects a reasonable bigger test approach, especially for higher polyphonies. For each test piece a mean value of maximum five refers to highest similarity while a mean value of zero refers to no correlation of each system test output with the reference stream.

5.4 Test scenarios

For each claimed hypothesis we implement one or several algorithms as indicated to be required by the hypothesis. We run our software system on the same input tracks with the same instrument types and the same sequence of notes within one test setup. For each test setup we enable or disable algorithm parts or we change parameters steering the behaviour of the particular algorithm. Since this research work did not achieve a reasonable good quality to set up sophisticated tests for higher polyphonies and different instrument type groups, any test analysis with MANOVA and the Tukey test are sadly omitted. The claimed hypotheses are evaluated on the subjective listening test results scientifically by employing the one-way ANOVA paradigm.

5.4.1 Test one - Spectral peak classification

We choose a melody and bass line from an Accordeon, apply a pitch-transposition of factor 1.4 and compare the performance of the monophonic track for the melody, evaluated in a monophonic alone and together with the bass line in a polyphonic environment. In order to verify the impact of examining the spectral shape contour of the measured spectral peak regions we create four different test pieces.

1. Piece:

- Parameter setup achieving a high qualitative distinction between valid and scrambled spectral peak region types
- Pure algorithm transforming only the selected valid peak regions to the new TF plane

2. Piece:

- Exclusive selection of spectral peak regions being marked as non-overlapped from the MIDI score
- Pure algorithm transforming only the selected valid peak regions to the new TF plane

3. Piece:

- Parameter setup achieving a high qualitative distinction between valid and scrambled spectral peak region types
- All algorithms enabled to treat each evaluated spectral peak region accordingly

4. Piece:

- Exclusive selection of spectral peak regions being marked as non-overlapped from the MIDI score
- All algorithms enabled to treat each evaluated spectral peak region accordingly

All algorithms enabled refers to the activation of transient modelling, harmonic peak generation, nearest neighbour interpolation and AM beating magnitude correction. The naming convention is not completely true because the plain -6 dB magnitude correction is disabled.

5.4.1.1 Objective evaluation measurements

We compare the results between the four tests and expect that piece two and four perform worse than piece one and three because of not complying to hypothesis one. We select to list those objective measurements in the following table 5.1 exhibiting the highest difference inbetween them and possibly validating to the most the assumptions from the first hypothesis.

	Piece 1	Piece 2	Piece 3	Piece 4
1. Measure	437.34	380.38	369.41	433.56
2. Measure	1.87	2.07	1.24	0.51
3. Measure	4200.66	9930.77	10872.08	3930.13
4. Measure	40.12	252.85	90.63	42.13

Table 5.1: Objective measurements - Test one

1. Measure: Pearson-Correlation on LPC
2. Measure: Difference-Summation of Waveform-Samples
3. Measure: Euclidean Distance of Waveform-Samples
4. Measure: Euclidean Distance of MFCC

We immediately conclude from these values that our assumptions are not completely validated. The output measured for piece two is worse as expected due to the combination of a poor peak selection along with less sophisticated algorithms following this input in order to produce a new TF plane. But piece four behaves better than expected. As input it receives exclusively non-overlapped peak region without a check on their spectral shape which doesn't deteriorate the output quality because the following sophisticated algorithms deal in a good manner in producing a qualitative new TF plane. We note that we can rely on the simple knowledge from the MIDI score to select non-overlapped peak regions if we employ harmonic insertion and/or nearest neighbour interpolation.

5.4.1.2 Subjective listening test results

The corresponding mean values for the four test pieces of the executed listening test one are given in table 5.2.

	Piece 1	Piece 2	Piece 3	Piece 4
Mean value	3.33	1.0	1.89	3.22

Table 5.2: Subjective listening test results - Test one

From this test result we calculate an overall mean value of 2.36, along with a variance of 0.9378. The results of the corresponding one-way ANOVA are listed in table 5.3.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Fisher F-value	Significance (p)
Between Groups	33.759	3	11.253	9.182	0.000
Within Groups	39.217	32	1.226		
Total	72.976	35			

Table 5.3: ANOVA analysis - Test one

We can reject the null hypothesis at a significance level of F-value 9.0 as well as a p-value of zero and claim a significant difference between the test excerpts.

5.4.1.3 Hypothesis evaluation - Test one

From the objective and subjective evaluation we conclude the existence of an alternative hypothesis. However, this statement is just valid to proof the existence of differences between the groups of single test excerpts but not to claim a statistical significance of one algorithm, being part of two groups, against another algorithm. Without calculating the Tukey test between each mean value pairs it is apparent that piece one and four validate the Null hypothesis H_0 . Since these two pieces contain all four different algorithmic paradigms to be evaluated for this test the conclusion is that we cannot claim a statistical significant hypothesis stating that we exclusively have to rely on the MIDI score or the spectral peak classification algorithm in order to select valid spectral peak regions. With this the first hypothesis is rejected.

5.4.2 Test two - Energy correction paradigms

We choose again the melody line from the Accordeon, this time together with the same bass line according to the score, but from a Piano. We apply a time-scaling factor of 1.3 and compare again the monophonic and polyphonic performance of the melody line. We enable or disable different algorithmic paradigms influencing the energy distribution in the new TF plane.

1. Piece:

- Magnitude correction according to the maximum of the input region as input for transient modelling, harmonic insertion and nearest neighbour interpolation
- Additional correction of magnitudes in the new TF plane when AM beating can be exploited for one sinusoid in overlapped regions

2. Piece:

- Magnitude correction according to the DFT bin of the input region where the peak of the new spectral region is inserted by transient modelling, harmonic insertion and nearest neighbour interpolation
- Additional correction of magnitudes in the new TF plane when AM beating can be exploited for one sinusoid in overlapped regions
- Additional correction of -6 dB on peak region being tagged as overlapped

3. Piece:

- Magnitude correction according to the DFT bin of the input region where the peak of the new spectral region is inserted by transient modelling, harmonic insertion and nearest neighbour interpolation

4. Piece:

- Pure transformation algorithm on valid peak regions (no transient modelling, no harmonic insertion, no nearest neighbour interpolation)
- Additional correction of magnitudes in the new TF plane when AM beating can be exploited for one sinusoid in overlapped regions
- Additional correction of -6 dB on peak region being tagged as overlapped

5. Piece:

- Pure transformation algorithm on valid peak regions (no transient modelling, no harmonic insertion, no nearest neighbour interpolation)
- Additional correction of magnitudes in the new TF plane when AM beating can be exploited for one sinusoid in overlapped regions
- Additional correction of magnitudes in the new TF plane when FM beating can be exploited for a second sinusoid in overlapped regions

5.4.2.1 Objective evaluation measurements

The selection and combination of algorithms trying to correct the energy and producing an high qualitative new TF plane appears to be chosen not very well. This is because not one algorithm achieves significantly better results than the others. This statement is validated more by the notion that despite harmonic insertion and nearest neighbour interpolation work reasonably well, the status of implementation for AM/FM beating exploitation, being the main part for the required energy correction to distinct well between different sources, is not completely satisfying. Plain energy correction by -6 dB is expected to achieve not a high performance. The correction of the magnitudes for the inserted peak regions does not address different sources. The only expectation drawn from short experiments while the software implementation is that FM beating deteriorates completely the output stream.

	Piece 1	Piece 2	Piece 3	Piece 4	Piece 5
1. Measure	0.85	0.77	0.92	0.82	0.07
2. Measure	90.77	88.64	69.95	80.02	118.30
3. Measure	7026.85	7859.21	4040.20	7645.68	14865.55

Table 5.4: Objective measurements - Test two

1. Measure: Pearson-Correlation on Waveform-Samples
2. Measure: Euclidean Distance of MFCC
3. Measure: Euclidean Distance of Waveform-Samples

In table 5.4 we examine clearly no big difference between the pieces one, two and four while piece three, where no exploitation of AM beating is executed, achieves the best result for this test. This leads to the conclusion that as well the implementation of AM beating for magnitude correction is not correct. Piece five has as expected an apparently low correlation with the reference waveform and exhibits higher Euclidean distances.

5.4.2.2 Subjective listening test results

The corresponding mean values for the five test pieces of the executed listening test two are given in table 5.5.

	Piece 1	Piece 2	Piece 3	Piece 4	Piece 5
Mean value	3.11	2.44	3.33	2.78	0.44

Table 5.5: Subjective listening test results - Test two

From this test result we calculate an overall mean value of 2.42. The results of the corresponding one-way ANOVA are listed in table 5.6.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Fisher F-value	Significance (p)
Between Groups	48.191	4	12.048	3.696	0.012
Within Groups	130.390	40	3.260		
Total	178.581	44			

Table 5.6: ANOVA analysis - Test two

Despite a p-value below 5 %, the F-value does not exceed the critical expectation threshold, set for this test to 9. We cannot state a significant difference to evaluate an alternative hypothesis.

5.4.2.3 Hypothesis evaluation - Test two

We skip the scientific analysis of pair-wise mean value comparison with the Tukey test because of the one-way ANOVA result and reject therefore the claimed hypothesis two. This result is mainly caused by the low quality achieved for the current status of implementation. The indication to employ AM/FM beating in order to calculate and correct the magnitudes and phases of spectral peak regions in overlapped frequency regions remains.

5.4.3 Test three - Harmonic Insertion vs. Nearest Neighbour Interpolation

For the third test we apply a lower and higher melody line, the latter one being again the test excerpt from the Accordeon for the subjective listening test. The lower melody line from a Piano has pauses inbetween and interrupts the melody line not all the time, which was the case for the first two tests. We apply a time-scaling and pitch-transposition factor of 0.8 and employ a well chosen parameter setup achieving a high qualitative distinction between valid and scrambled spectral peak region types.

1. Piece: Nearest Neighbour interpolation and Harmonic Insertion
2. Piece: Nearest Neighbour interpolation
3. Piece: Harmonic Insertion
4. Piece: Pure algorithm transforming only the selected valid peak regions to the new TF plane

5.4.3.1 Objective evaluation measurements

For this test setup we expect for the first three pieces a high correlation and less distance to the reference output and the contrary for the fourth output.

	Piece 1	Piece 2	Piece 3	Piece 4
1. Measure	0.81	0.19	0.30	0.32
2. Measure	0.95	0.94	0.94	0.93
3. Measure	104.01	103.66	98.69	97.96
4. Measure	2.51	2.52	2.45	2.46

Table 5.7: Objective measurements - Test three

1. Measure: Difference-Summation of Waveform-Samples
2. Measure: Pearson-Correlation on Waveform-Samples
3. Measure: Euclidean Distance of MFCC
4. Measure: Difference-Summation of LSF

The values shown in table do not verify the expectations for this test. Only the first measure for piece two exhibits an apparently lower difference to the reference output, while all other objective measurements show no statistically significant difference.

5.4.3.2 Subjective listening test results

The corresponding mean values for the four test pieces of the executed listening test three are given in table 5.8.

	Piece 1	Piece 2	Piece 3	Piece 4
Mean value	3.44	3.33	3.0	3.22

Table 5.8: Subjective listening test results - Test three

The test results of the subjective listening test for test three verify the objective measurements. From this listening test results we calculate an overall mean value of 3.2475 and a variance of 0.1627. The results for the corresponding one-way ANOVA are listed in table 5.9.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Fisher F-value	Significance (p)
Between Groups	0.953	3	0.318	2.462	0.080
Within Groups	4.129	32	0.129		
Total	5.082	35			

Table 5.9: ANOVA analysis - Test three

The subjective and objective evaluation results are reflected by the one-way ANOVA. The F-value is not high enough to indicate a significant difference between the measured data, which can be already concluded by visual inspection from both tables.

5.4.3.3 Hypothesis evaluation - Test three

As well the Null hypothesis H_0 for hypothesis three is validated. We cannot claim any measured nor perceived significant difference between the algorithms Harmonic Insertion or Nearest Neighbour interpolation, nor a combination or non of them.

Chapter 6

Summary

The biggest crime of a musician is to play notes instead of playing music
- Isaac Stern

6.1 Conclusions

We summarize different points of observations drawn from this research approach.

1. Energy correction:

The main problem remaining for this work is how to correct the energy distribution in overlapped frequency region due to not knowing from a MIDI score the energy for each spectral frame and sinusoidal component. The main approach of this research work, the exploitation of AM/FM beating, could not be brought to a reasonable status in order to retrieve the true magnitude of the occurring overlapped partials and to correct their energy. An additional algorithm could employ a damped exponential curve approximating the decrease in energy from lower to higher frequency components in order to correct the energy of each measured peak region accordingly. Another approach could measure in a monophonic environment for each track and frame the energy of partials and steer with this knowledge the harmonic estimation and processing functions to precisely correct the energy. This is avoided because of less practical impact referring to a later real-world application for processing audio objects in a musical piece with the information from a corresponding MIDI score.

2. Fundamental frequency f_0 dependency:

As expected problems arise deteriorating the performance of estimating each monophonic track from the polyphonic stream when a bigger amount of harmonic partials is overlapped in frequency, and thus as well in energy. For the

subjective listening tests the monophonic track comprising the highest notes in frequency were chosen because of sharing the least amount of its own harmonic partials with other sources and thus achieving the best perceptual performance. Notes with lower fundamental frequencies from especially the bass line did not achieve a sufficient perceptual separation from other sources and had thus to be excluded from the listening test where participants would have only been able to evaluate which excerpt sounds less worse.

3. Algorithmic influence on perceptual performance:

Throughout this research approach care was taken to implement exact algorithms without producing errors resulting in perceptual artefacts. This theoretical guideline had to be rejected on certain points. Each algorithmic step was advanced by checking its influence precisely on the values stored in vectors it treats, by plotting the phase and magnitude spectrum and printing values to data files for further inspection. After finalizing one algorithm part with certainty to not introduce errors the new system was tested on its overall behaviour, the audio output stream. Several times the set thresholds for the new algorithmic part being heuristically retrieved from value vectors did deteriorate the audio quality and had to be re-evaluated by running different listening tests.

6.2 Future work

6.2.1 Partial tracking

Lagrange proposes in [Lagrange et al., 2003] an algorithm to track partials in polyphonic sounds based on linear prediction, which is defined in time domain but can be employed as tracking mechanism for harmonic partials in the spectral domain as well. The first instantaneous estimation of peaks in the spectrum is linked to the peaks of successive frames to establish a continuous partial trajectory, assuming a stationary frequency evolution of voiced signals. The maximal frequency difference allowed between the spectral peaks of adjacent frames is given by equation 6.1.

$$|f_p(k + 1) - f_p(k)| < \Delta f \tag{6.1}$$

The peak p_i^{k+1} with the lowest difference in frequency to p_i^k is selected to continue an established partial trajectory for a partial with index i . If no peak could be found within the frequency range Δf , the partial trajectory is terminated and labelled as “dead”. The synthesis quality is improved by adding a zero-amplitude peak with extrapolated frequency and phase at the beginning and the end of one partial trajectory.

Decreasing amplitudes and strong modulations can lead to missing peaks not being

selected. Adding a “zombie” state to a limited number of frames if a partial cannot link to any peak in a frame decreases this problem but introduces a possible diverge from the true partial trajectory. Therefore a linear combination of the past evolution of the partials predicts their optimal future evolution. A linear prediction model of order d estimates the FIR filter coefficients of a vector a_i evaluating p past samples in order to predict the sample \hat{x} , expressed by equation 6.2.

$$\hat{x}(n) = \sum_{i=1}^p a_i \cdot x(n - i) \quad (6.2)$$

6.2.2 Harmonic trajectory estimation and correction

In [Bonada, 2008] another approach to estimate and track the trajectory of harmonic partials is discussed. Since this work addresses additionally the transformation in time and frequency of sinusoidal components, as required for this research approach, it may be better suited as continuation for a future extension of this paper.

Having estimated the continuation of harmonic partials with the paradigms of linear prediction or harmonic trajectory estimation, an algorithm to smooth the trajectories of each spectral peak regions magnitude $|X|$, phase θ and frequency ω over frames is required to minimize or avoid artefacts, as already indicated at the end of chapter 4.4.4. This was not implemented due to the time restrictions given for the thesis.

6.2.3 Towards a semi-automatic system

The intention for this research work was to show ways how to accomplish a software system processing audio content in a polyphonic environment using knowledge from a MIDI score. Finally we employed pre-annotated frame-wise f_0 information from monophonic f_0 estimation algorithms. We did not evaluate the performance in terms of output quality dependent on different input scores using a MIDI file directly. Further work could evaluate and compare the following scenarios.

- Frame-wise timing and f_0 information from pre-annotated scores.
- Note-wise timing and f_0 information from MIDI notes.
- Note-wise timing and f_0 information from MIDI notes plus supervised and modified monophonic f_0 estimation algorithms for frame-wise improvements, as mentioned in chapter 3.3.6.

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